

QUANTUM COMPUTING SOLUTIONS FOR UNSTRUCTURED SEARCH

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DECLARATION

I certify that this dissertation does not incorporate without acknowledgment, any material previously submitted for a Degree or Diploma in any university, and to the best of my knowledge and belief it does not contain any material previously published or written or orally communicated by other people except where due reference is made in the text.

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ABSTRACT

Quantum computing which uses basic quantum mechanical principles such as superposition and entanglement, is an emerging field of computing with the ability to significantly speed up the process of finding solutions for certain problems. The noise, which is inevitable to occur in prototype quantum computers in this so-called “Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ)” era, is the main concern regarding further advancements in this field. In this study, the performance of currently available NISQ devices was investigated using a class of popular quantum algorithms, namely, quantum search algorithms. The famous quantum search algorithm called Grover’s algorithm is claimed to provide a quadratic speedup over any classical algorithm in finding a marked search item in an unsorted list. In this study, Grover’s algorithm was implemented for two-qubit, three-qubit, and four-qubit search spaces, and was tested on real quantum processors, as well as quantum simulators. The results obtained from the simulator were found to be in agreement with the theoretically-predicted results within the error bars. The device always yielded lower probabilities for finding the correct search item than the simulator. The results from the device deviated further from the simulation/theoretical results as the number of qubits in the search space increased. Therefore, it was predicted that the noise and other errors present in the internal hardware of a device play a significant role. The effect of running multiple iterations of the Grover operation was investigated for both the simulator and the device. The best results on the device were observed for a single Grover iteration, and the results progressively got worse with each new iteration. The results from the simulator continuously improved with each iteration, until a certain optimal number of iterations is reached. In this study, measurement error mitigation techniques were used to minimize the effect of measurement errors in the quantum device. This technique only yielded a marginal improvement in the results. The quantum random walk search algorithm is another type of quantum search algorithm, which is perceived to be the quantum equivalent of the classical random walk. In this study, Grover’s algorithm and the quantum random walk search algorithm were compared for the 4-qubit search spaces on the quantum simulator. It was observed that both algorithms provide approximately equal results.

Key Words – Grover’s algorithm, quantum random walk search algorithm, measurement error mitigation, IBM quantum processors, NISQ devices.

TABLE OF CONTENT

1	INTRODUCTION	1
1.1	Quantum computing versus classical computing	1
1.2	Quantum search algorithms.....	2
1.3	Quantum hardware and software.....	3
1.4	The significance of the study	6
1.5	Objectives of the study.....	6
1.6	Outline of the thesis.....	7
2	BACKGROUND	8
2.1	Evolution of quantum mechanics.....	8
2.2	Evolution of computer science.....	8
2.3	Evolution of quantum computing.....	9
2.4	History of quantum search algorithms	10
2.4.1	Grover’s algorithm.....	10
2.4.2	Quantum random walk search algorithm.....	11
2.5	Evolution of quantum computing hardware.....	12
3	THEORY	13
3.1	A concise review of linear algebra.....	13
3.1.1	Complex vectors	13
3.1.2	Inner product.....	13
3.1.3	Orthonormal bases	13
3.1.4	Linear operators	14
3.1.5	Outer product	14
3.2	Quantum mechanics of two-level systems	15
3.2.1	Qubit	15
3.2.2	Linear operations on qubits.....	15
3.2.3	Multiple-qubit states and tensor product.....	15

3.3	Fundamentals in quantum computing	16
3.3.1	Circuit diagrams.....	16
3.3.2	Visual representation of qubit states using Bloch sphere	17
3.3.3	Single qubit gates.....	18
3.3.4	Multiple qubits and entangled states.....	19
3.4	Grover’s algorithm	21
3.4.1	The oracle.....	21
3.4.2	The algorithmic procedure.....	24
3.5	Geometric interpretation of Grover’s algorithm	25
3.5.1	The optimal number of Grover iterations to a search problem.....	27
3.5.2	The limit to the number of iterations needed.....	28
3.5.3	The effect of running Grover’s algorithm for more than the optimal number of iterations.....	29
3.6	Quantum random walk search algorithm	31
3.6.1	Classical random walk	31
3.6.2	Quantum walk.....	31
3.6.3	The coined quantum walks	31
3.6.4	Coin operator	31
3.6.5	The shift operator (\mathcal{S}).....	32
3.6.6	Quantum walk search algorithm	33
3.6.7	Quantum phase estimation (QPE).....	35
4	METHODOLOGY	37
4.1	IBM cloud-based platform for quantum computing	37
4.1.1	QISKIT package	38
4.1.2	QISKIT Aer simulator	38
4.2	Selecting the most appropriate quantum backend for the study.....	38
4.3	Construction of the Grover’s algorithm	41

4.3.1	Creating the oracle circuit.....	41
4.3.2	The complete oracle circuit.....	42
4.3.3	Creating the diffusion circuit	44
4.3.4	Creating the complete Grover circuit.....	46
4.4	Transpiling quantum circuits to utilize different physical qubits on the backend	47
4.5	Construction of the quantum random walk search algorithm	48
4.5.1	Reflection about the state \mathbf{B}	48
4.5.2	Reflection about the state \mathbf{U}	49
5	ReSULTS AND ANALYSIS	51
5.1	A comparison of Grover’s search results: simulator versus IBM quantum processors	51
5.1.1	Theoretical analysis of the results for the three-qubit algorithm	52
5.1.2	Results for finding each search item from different solution spaces	57
5.2	Comparison of the two-qubit Grover’s search for different connecting qubit pairs .	59
5.3	Comparison of the results on different backends	60
5.4	Grover’s search with multiple search items	62
5.5	The effect of the number of Grover iterations on the performance of the Grover’s search	64
5.5.1	2-qubit Grover’s algorithm	64
5.5.2	3-qubit Grover’s algorithm	65
5.5.3	4-qubit Grover’s algorithm	66
5.6	Mitigating measurement errors using calibration matrices	69
5.7	The four-qubit quantum random walk search algorithm.....	72
5.7.1	Comparison of the Grover’s algorithm and the quantum random walk search algorithm for a single search item.....	72
5.7.2	The effect of the number of iterations on the performance of the quantum random walk search.....	73
6	DISCUSSION.....	75

7	CONCLUSIONs	78
8	APPENDIX.....	86
8.1	Oracle circuits for 2-qubit, 3-qubit, and 4-qubit Grover’s algorithm implementations 86	
8.1.1	2-qubit Grover’s search.....	86
8.1.2	3-qubit Grover’s search.....	86
8.1.3	4-qubit Grover’s search.....	87
8.2	Basic codes used in the study	89
8.2.1	The sample code for creating a general oracle.....	89
8.2.2	The sample code for creating a general diffusor.....	89
8.2.3	The sample code for creating a general full Grover circuit	90
8.3	Theoretical analysis of the results for the two-qubit algorithm	91
8.4	Theoretical analysis of the results for the four-qubit algorithm.....	94

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1-1 (Left) The analogy for data stored in a classical bit is given by a mechanical switch consisting of “on” and “off” states. The image is taken from (*Set of electric wall switch in ON and OFF mode*). (Right) The qubit is represented as a superposition of the state $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$. This leads to infinitely many possible states..... 1

Figure 1-2 An array consisting of N number of elements is represented. The square marked in red is the marked search item. The image is taken from (*Grover’s algorithm - IBM Quantum*)2

Figure 1-3 (Left) The objective of quantum annealing is to find the global minimum of a cost function when the cost function landscape is rugged. It avoids getting trapped in a local minimum by tunneling through energy barriers. The image is taken from (*Quantum Annealing — Steemit*). (Right) In circuit-based quantum computing, a quantum algorithm is realized by a network of quantum gates, which is referred to as a quantum circuit.3

Figure 1-4 A hydrogen atom with two energy levels (ground state and first excited state) can be occupied as a qubit.4

Figure 1-5 (Left) In earlier quantum computers, trapped-ion technology was more commonly used. The image is taken from (Hui, 2019). (Right) According to the current trend, most of today’s quantum processors use superconducting qubits. The image is taken from (Cohen, 2014).5

Figure 1-6 (Left) The quantum processor known as the “Eagle” is said to be the most powerful one that IBM possesses, which was introduced in 2021. The image is taken from (*IBM Unveils Breakthrough 127-Qubit Quantum Processor, 2021*). (Right) The actual look of a quantum computer, which requires a carefully controlled environment and conditions. The image is taken from (*IBM Q Experience Strives To Bring Quantum Computing To Masses - Quantum: Machine Learning & Analytics, 2020*).....5

Figure 3-1 (Left) An example of a normal Boolean circuit. The image is taken from (Kyang, 2018). (Right) An example of a simple quantum circuit drawn in QISKIT. 17

Figure 3-2 The representation of a qubit using the Bloch sphere. The image is taken from (Warke, 2019) 17

Figure 3-3 The Bloch sphere representation of the $|0\rangle$ state (first from left), $|1\rangle$ state (second from left), $+\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)$ state (third from left), and $+\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle - |1\rangle)$ state (fourth from left). 18

Figure 3-4 The application of an X gate rotates the qubit 180 degrees on the X-axis as shown in the Bloch sphere representation. 18

Figure 3-5 (Left) The transformation of the state $|0\rangle$ to $|+\rangle$ is shown in the Bloch sphere representation. (Right) The transformation of the state $|1\rangle$ to $|-\rangle$ is shown using the Bloch sphere notation. 19

Figure 3-6 A Hadamard gate and an X-gate are applied to the first and the second qubit respectively. 19

Figure 3-7 Circuit representation of the CNOT gate. In this representation, $q0$ is the control bit while $q1$ is the target bit. 21

Figure 3-8 The Q-sphere representation of the multi-qubit state $| - + \rangle = \frac{1}{2}(|00\rangle + |01\rangle - |10\rangle - |11\rangle)$. Note that $|10\rangle$ and $|11\rangle$ states have a phase difference of π , shown as yellow blobs. 21

Figure 3-9 The general oracle can be defined as shown in the figure. If the oracle qubit is measured to be $|1\rangle$, then $|x\rangle$ is a solution to the search problem. 22

Figure 3-10 The action of the oracle in Grover's algorithm is expressed using quantum circuit notation. Here, the oracle qubit is initialized to the $-$ state. The state of the oracle qubit remains unchanged throughout the process. 23

Figure 3-11 The complete Grover circuit consisting of the oracle followed by the diffusion operator. Here, $H^{\otimes n}$ represents the Hadamard transform, Uf represents the oracle, and $U \neq 0n$ represents the phase shift operation. 25

Figure 3-12 The complex vector space spanned by the $|\alpha\rangle$ and $|\beta\rangle$ states which are orthonormal, exposing the complete solution space. The initial state $|\psi\rangle$ makes an angle of $\theta/2$ with $|\alpha\rangle$. The $|\psi\rangle$ state is reflected about the state $|\alpha\rangle$ by the oracle operation where $O|\psi\rangle$ represents the consequent state. After that, $O|\psi\rangle$ state is again reflected about $|\psi\rangle$, where the consequent state is represented by $G|\psi\rangle$. After the two consecutive reflections, the initial state $|\psi\rangle$ now have been rotated toward the state $|\beta\rangle$ by an angle θ . The image is taken from (Nielsen and Chuang, 2011). 26

Figure 3-13 The initial state ψ is defined in the complex vector space spanned by α and β . .. 27

Figure 3-14 The walker is stationed at the state $|2\rangle$ (as shown by the red dot), and depending on the outcome of the coin, it can move to the state $|1\rangle$ or state $|3\rangle$ 32

Figure 3-15 The operation of the phase oracle. The state U' is a superposition of states U and $U \perp$. The phase oracle reflects the state U' about $|U\rangle$ according to the linear mapping given in equations (49) and (50). 34

Figure 3-16 A high-level circuit diagram illustrating the quantum phase estimation algorithm.	35
Figure 3-17 The complete circuit for quantum phase estimation, including the inverse QFT (Quantum Fourier Transform) operation.	36
Figure 4-1 The graphical user interface of the IBM cloud-computing platform provides up-to-date details about the quantum backends available for running quantum algorithms written by the users. Details of four backends are shown: <code>ibmq_nairobi</code> , <code>ibmq_jakarta</code> , <code>ibmq_quito</code> , and <code>ibmq_belem</code>	37
Figure 4-2 An example quantum circuit constructed using the QISKIT package. Using tools available in QISKIT, the circuit can be directly executed on IBM quantum processors or simulators.....	38
Figure 4-3 The error maps of the <code>ibmq_belem</code> (top) and <code>ibmq_santiago</code> (bottom) backends, which show the respective qubit-connectivity graphs and the error rates related to the backends.	40
Figure 4-4 A CZ gate can be created by sandwiching a CNOT gate between two Hadamard gates.	41
Figure 4-5 The oracle circuit for the 2-qubit case assuming that the state <code>00</code> is the search item.	42
Figure 4-6 The 3-qubit oracle circuit for finding the search item <code>001</code>	43
Figure 4-7 2-qubit, 3-qubit, and 4-qubit oracle circuits for selected search items.	44
Figure 4-8 The diffusor circuit for the 2-qubit Grover's algorithm.	45
Figure 4-9 The diffusor circuits for the 2-qubit Grover's algorithm (top), the 3-qubit Grover's algorithm (middle), and the 4-qubit Grover's algorithm (bottom).	46
Figure 4-10 The complete circuit for the 2-qubit Grover's algorithm for the search item <code> 00></code> . Note that Hadamard gate initialization is followed by the oracle, and then by the diffusor. Finally, the two qubits are measured.	46
Figure 4-11 The two-qubit Grover's algorithm designed using qubit 0 and qubit 1 (top). The transpiled circuit shows the final result of the numerous transformations the circuit undergoes in order to match the topology of the selected backend, <code>ibmq_belem</code> (bottom).....	47
Figure 4-12 The two-qubit Grover's algorithm designed using qubit 1 and qubit 3 (top). The transpiled circuit shows the final result of the numerous transformations the circuit undergoes in order to match the topology of the selected backend, <code>ibmq_belem</code> (bottom).....	48
Figure 4-13 The 4-qubit phase oracle implemented to find the search item <code>0110</code>	48

Figure 4-14 The quantum circuit for the composite operator W . It consists of the coin operator followed by the shift operator.49

Figure 4-15 This circuit puts a negative sign in front of the state if $\theta = 0$, and does nothing if $\theta \neq 0$49

Figure 4-16 The quantum circuit used for the operation of reflection about the state $|U\rangle$50

Figure 4-17 The complete quantum random walk search algorithm can be implemented in QISKIT following the two operations; reflection about the state B , and reflection about U . .50

Figure 5-1 The comparison between the results obtained from the Aer simulator (left) and the ibmq_belem device (right) for the 2-qubit Grover’s search. It shows that the quantum backend ibmq_belem is capable of providing reasonable results for the two-qubit search.51

Figure 5-2 The comparison between the results obtained from the Aer simulator (left) and the ibmq_belem device (right) results for the 3-qubit Grover’s search. The results differ by a considerable amount.52

Figure 5-3 The comparison between the results obtained from the Aer simulator (top) and the ibmq_belem device (bottom) for the 4-qubit Grover’s search. For the 4-qubit algorithm, ibmq_belem cannot provide reasonable results.52

Figure 5-4 (Left) The three qubits have been initialized using Hadamard gates. (Right) Bloch sphere representation shows that all three qubits are in $+$ state individually.53

Figure 5-5 The Q-sphere representation of the initial superposition state. Here, the probability amplitudes of all basis states are equal (12.5%).54

Figure 5-6 The Q-sphere representation of ψ_1 shows that the search item $|011\rangle$ now has a phase difference of π , in contrast to the other search items. (Yellow represents an angle of π).55

Figure 5-7 The Q-sphere representation of the final state ψ_2 . The basis state 011 is represented by a blob that is considerably larger than the other basis states. This indicates that 011 basis state has a much higher probability amplitude than the others.56

Figure 5-8 Results for the 2-qubit Grover’s search obtained using the Aer simulator (left) and ibmq_belem device (right). The color represents the measurement probability. The plots indicate only a marginal difference between the results obtained from the simulator and the device. .58

Figure 5-9 Results for the 3-qubit Grover’s search obtained using the Aer simulator (left) and ibmq_belem device (right). The color represents the measurement probability. The plots indicate a considerable difference between the results obtained from the simulator and the device. ...58

Figure 5-10 Results for the 4-qubit Grover’s search obtained using the Aer simulator (left) and ibm_belem device (right). The color represents the measurement probability. The 4-qubit search on the device does not produce satisfactory results when compared to the simulation results.58

Figure 5-11 The probability of finding the search element after designing the two-qubit Grover’s algorithm using different two-qubit combinations. 3-4 qubit pair gives the highest probability out of the four combinations considered.60

Figure 5-12 A comparison of the results for the 2-qubit Grover’s algorithm for the search item 10 on different quantum backends. All three backends were capable of producing reasonable results for the 2-qubit case.61

Figure 5-13 A comparison of the results for the 3-qubit Grover’s algorithm for the search item 011 on different quantum backends. The backend ibmq_bogota provided a significantly lower probability of finding the correct search item when compared to the other two devices.61

Figure 5-14 A comparison of the results for the 4-qubit Grover’s algorithm for the search item 1101 on different quantum backends. All three backends were unable to generate promising results for the 4-qubit search algorithm.62

Figure 5-15 Results of the three-qubit Grover’s search with search items 100 and 111. The graph compares the results obtained through the simulator with the results obtained through the ibmq_belem device.63

Figure 5-16 A comparison of the two-qubit Grover’s search results obtained using the simulator for a single iteration (left) and two iterations (right). The probability of measuring the search item is substantially decreased when the number of Grover iterations is increased to two. Here, the designated search item is $|00\rangle$64

Figure 5-17 A comparison of the two-qubit Grover’s search results obtained using the device for a single iteration (left) and two iterations (right). The probability of measuring the search item is substantially decreased when the number of Grover iterations is increased to two. Here, the designated search item is $|00\rangle$64

Figure 5-18 A comparison of the three-qubit Grover’s search results obtained using the simulator for a single iteration (top left), two iterations (top right), and three iterations (bottom left). The probability of measuring the search item improves up to two iterations, but it declines when running the algorithm beyond two iterations, which is the optimal number of iterations for the three-qubit case. Here, the designated search item is $|010\rangle$65

Figure 5-19 A comparison of the three-qubit Grover’s search results obtained using the device for a single iteration (top left), two iterations (top right), and three iterations (bottom left). The probability of measuring the search item gets progressively worse as the number of iterations is increased. Here, the designated search item is $|010\rangle$66

Figure 5-20 A comparison of the four-qubit Grover’s search results obtained using the simulator for a single iteration (first from top), two iterations (second from top), three iterations (third from top), and four iterations (fourth from top). The probability of measuring the search item improves up to three Grover iterations, but it declines when running the algorithm for three iterations, which is the optimal number of iterations for the four-qubit case. Here, the designated search item is $|0110\rangle$67

Figure 5-21 A comparison of the four-qubit Grover’s search results obtained using the device for a single iteration (first from top), two iterations (second from top), three iterations (third from top), and four iterations (fourth from top). In contrast to the results obtained using the simulator, the probability of measuring the search item does not notably change when the number of iterations is increased. Here, the designated search item is $|0110\rangle$67

Figure 5-22 A comparison of the four-qubit Grover’s search results obtained using the simulator for a single iteration (top left), two iterations (top right), and three iterations (bottom left). Here, all possible search items in the solution space are considered. The color represents the probability of measuring the correct search item. The results are progressively improved as the number of iterations is increased up to three, which is the optimal number of iterations for the four-qubit case.....68

Figure 5-23 The 2-qubit (top left), 3-qubit (top right), and 4-qubit (bottom left) calibration matrices for the `ibmq_belem` device. The color shading represents the probability of measuring a particular state given the prepared state.69

Figure 5-24 Comparison of the results obtained using the simulator, results obtained using the device, and the error-corrected results for the 2-qubit search algorithm.70

Figure 5-25 Comparison of the results obtained using the simulator, results obtained using the device, and the error-corrected results for the 3-qubit search algorithm.70

Figure 5-26 Comparison of the results obtained using the simulator, results obtained using the device, and the error-corrected results for the 4-qubit search algorithm.71

Figure 5-27 Comparison of the results obtained using the simulator, results obtained using the device, and the error-corrected results for the 3-qubit search algorithm for two search items (100 and 111).71

Figure 5-28 The results obtained using the simulator for the Grover’s algorithm (top) and the quantum random walk search algorithm (bottom). The results are approximately close to each other, while Grover’s algorithm gives a slightly higher probability of measuring the search item.72

Figure 5-29 A comparison of the four-qubit quantum random walk search results obtained using the simulator for a single iteration (first from top), two iterations (second from top), three iterations (third from top), and four iterations (fourth from top). The probability of measuring the search item improves up to three iterations, but it declines when running the algorithm beyond three iterations, which is the optimal number of iterations for the four-qubit quantum random walk search. 73

Figure 8-1 The complete set of oracles for the 2-qubit Grover’s search86

Figure 8-2 The complete set of oracles for the 3-qubit Grover’s search86

Figure 8-3 The complete set of oracles for the 3-qubit Grover’s search88

Figure 8-4 Oracle used for Grover’s search with multiple search items (100 and 111).....88

Figure 8-5 (Left) The two qubits have been initialized using Hadamard gates. (Right) Bloch sphere representation shows that both qubits are in the + state individually.91

Figure 8-6 The Q-sphere representation of the initial superposition state. Here, the probability amplitudes of all basis states are equal (25%).91

Figure 8-7 The Q-sphere representation of ψ_1 shows that the search item $|10\rangle$ now has a phase difference of π , in contrast to the other search items. (Yellow represents an angle of π)......92

Figure 8-8 The Q-sphere representation of the final state ψ_2 . Only 10 state remains in the complex vector space.93

Figure 8-9 (Left) The four qubits have been initialized using Hadamard gates. (Right) Bloch sphere representation shows that both qubits are in the + state individually.94

Figure 8-10 The Q-sphere representation of the initial superposition state. Here, the probability amplitudes of all basis states are equal (6.25%).94

Figure 8-11 The Q-sphere representation of ψ_1 shows that the search item $|1101\rangle$ now has a phase difference of π , in contrast to the other search items. (Yellow represents an angle of π).95

Figure 8-12 The Q-sphere representation of the final state ψ_2 . The basis state 1101 is represented by a blob that is considerably larger than the other basis states. This indicates that 1101 basis state has a much higher probability amplitude than the others.96

LIST OF TABLES

Table 3-1 Classical truth table for the CNOT gate	20
Table 5-1 Probabilities of measuring the correct search item in the 2-qubit, 3-qubit, and 4-qubit Grover's search. The table compares the results from the theoretical analysis with the results obtained through the simulator and the ibmq_belem device.	57
Table 5-2 The connecting qubits in ibmq_belem backend and their gate error percentage	59
Table 5-3 Probabilities of measuring the correct search item in one, two, three, and four Grover iterations. The table compares Grover's algorithm results and the quantum random walk search results.	74

ABBREVIATIONS

QISKIT	– Quantum Information Software Kit
IBM	– International Business Machines
DFT	– Discrete Fourier Transformation
QFT	– Quantum Fourier Transformation
QPE	– Quantum Phase Estimation
NISQ	– Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum

1 INTRODUCTION

Quantum computing research today looks beyond the incredible union between computer science and quantum mechanics and is capable of addressing some ubiquitous problems in the real world. The rapid pace of the developments in the field paves the way for significant applications of quantum computing in the near future, not only in physics but also in other areas.

1.1 Quantum computing versus classical computing

Information is stored in a classical computer in the form of 1 and 0 (known as a classical bit, or a bit), which is similar to the process of turning on and off a mechanical switch. In other words, only two states exist. But on the other hand, the qubit which is known as the quantum analog of a classical bit can be in a state of superposition of the states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ (Nielsen and Chuang, 2011). Therefore, both states can be utilized simultaneously where the fundamental theory is governed by quantum mechanics. For a five-bit classical computer, only one of the thirty-two values can be encoded whereas its quantum counterpart is capable of encoding all of the thirty-two possibilities simultaneously. In the general case, an n -qubit quantum computer can be used to encode 2^n possibilities of classical bits, which signifies its exponential power of encoding information. In addition to that, the quantum computing model uses other quantum mechanical properties such as interference, and quantum entanglement to perform calculations.

Figure 1-1 (Left) The analogy for data stored in a classical bit is given by a mechanical switch consisting of “on” and “off” states. The image is taken from (*Set of electric wall switch in ON and OFF mode*). (Right) The qubit is represented as a superposition of the state $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$. This leads to infinitely many possible states.

Quantum computing is capable of solving certain problems significantly faster than classical computing. One such example is prime factorization, for which the famous Shor’s algorithm promises an exponential speedup over any classical algorithm (Peter *et al.*, 1994). As such, quantum computing is expected to transform the field of cryptography and is considered a threat to current algorithms related to cryptography (Mavroeidis *et al.*, 2018). For this same reason, there is a demand for new quantum cryptographic algorithms considering network and internet security.

Even though there exists some higher level of expectation towards the theoretically proven power of quantum computing, it faces a few immense challenges as it evolves. The quantum systems tend to interact with the outside environment resulting quantum decoherence (Schlosshauer, 2019). Therefore, the system should be isolated. But on the contrary, one has to control the quantum system properly, considering the interactions of the qubits inside the system. Additionally, the quantum decoherence and the noise existing in the quantum devices are the two main setbacks in quantum hardware (Preskill, 2018). Following that, some error mitigation techniques have been introduced to correct these errors to make these quantum devices more reliable and efficient (Endo, Benjamin and Li, 2018).

1.2 Quantum search algorithms

Finding a particular item, from a solution space is a common problem that humans face usually. Searching for a key to open up a door, out of a key ring can be regarded as a common example. Being more technical, finding a record related to a student from a database, can be mentioned. In either case, the fundamental approach is the same. The most efficient method is to start from the beginning and search for every key or record. If it is someone's lucky day, he may find it quite easily at the beginning of the course of the search, but it is also possible to find it as the very last element in the solution space. Therefore, on average, the person has to check $\frac{N}{2}$ items. But quantum search algorithms are capable of finding the item with just \sqrt{N} steps, which is an outstanding quadratic speedup (Peter *et al.*, 1994). Therefore, it has an algorithmic complexity of $O(\sqrt{N})$, compared to its classical counterpart which has a complexity of $O(N)$ (Kim, Han and Jeong, 2018).

Figure 1-2 An array consisting of N number of elements is represented. The square marked in red is the marked search item. The image is taken from (*Grover's algorithm - IBM Quantum*)

In a more technical sense, the search problem is one type of problem, where the solutions are sought, such that a pre-defined statement is true. As common examples, database searching and sorting problems could be mentioned. There exist two main types of search problems; unstructured search and structured search. Grover's algorithm solves the unstructured search problem. In an unstructured search problem, the structure of the solution space is unknown.

But in contrast to that, in a structured search problem, information about the structure is known. Sometimes, there are patterns in the organization of the data that make them easily searchable. In general, solving a structured search problem is not that difficult when compared to unstructured search problems.

The quadratic speed up attainable through the quantum search algorithms is substantial particularly when the size of the database or the array is large (Korepin and Xu, 2009). However, the applications of Grover’s algorithm go beyond the general database search since the search algorithm can be portrayed as an equation or a constraint satisfaction problem (Campbell, Khurana and Montanaro, 2019). This representation is helpful for the further development of the applications of Grover’s algorithms, such as quantum random walk, quantum counting, etc.

1.3 Quantum hardware and software

There are different models of quantum computing, and two of the most famous ones are the quantum circuit model and quantum annealing. In quantum annealing, the Hamiltonian of a quantum system is systematically evolved such that it can be used to solve a specific problem (Finnila *et al.*, 1994). The final state of the quantum system after the evolution is considered the answer (Albash and Lidar, 2018). Quantum annealers are primarily used for solving discrete optimization problems, which are commonly encountered in many disciplines such as finance, engineering, material sciences, machine learning, etc. (Battaglia, Santoro and Tosatti, 2005)

Figure 1-3 (Left) The objective of quantum annealing is to find the global minimum of a cost function when the cost function landscape is rugged. It avoids getting trapped in a local minimum by tunneling through energy barriers. The image is taken from (*Quantum Annealing — Steemit*). (Right) In circuit-based quantum computing, a quantum algorithm is realized by a network of quantum gates, which is referred to as a quantum circuit.

The operations are characterized by several gates in the gate-based quantum computers. In a way, this model resembles much more equivalence to classical computers (Leymann and Barzen, 2020). Regarding the implementation of digital quantum computers, the basic building

block is the qubit. It is accepted that quantum systems with two levels can be exploited as qubits. A hydrogen atom with two levels is a common example. Other than that, a polarized photon, the spin of an electron, and the current generated in a superconducting circuit can be utilized as a qubit (Qiang *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 1-4 A hydrogen atom with two energy levels (ground state and first excited state) can be occupied as a qubit.

In addition to that, a quantum computer should be able to initialize qubits and must have an appropriate decoherence time to complete the computation properly (Duan and Guo, 1998). Similarly, it should be able to measure the qubits to exploit the output data after the computation phase is ended. As previously mentioned, different technologies have been used by different companies and institutes when constructing qubits. IBM, Intel, D-Wave, Google, and Microsoft are among the leading competitors in the advancement of these current quantum computing technologies (Shin *et al.*, 2014; AI Quantum, 2020).

The trapped-ion technology was one of the preliminary technologies introduced to quantum computers, where the electrons are removed from the atoms and the resulting positively charged ions are manipulated by electric fields (Bruzewicz *et al.*, 2019). In the current era, superconducting qubits are more popular among companies, where artificial two-level quantum systems are created with the aid of superconducting materials, whereas the states are controlled by microwave pulses (Huang *et al.*, 2020).

Figure 1-5 (Left) In earlier quantum computers, trapped-ion technology was more commonly used. The image is taken from (Hui, 2019). (Right) According to the current trend, most of today’s quantum processors use superconducting qubits. The image is taken from (Cohen, 2014).

IBM is one of the leading companies in quantum computing. The superconducting qubit technology has been their primarily used technology and they have been increasing the number of available qubits in quantum processors throughout the last decade. In addition to that, their publicly accessible “IBMQ Experience” program provided 5 qubit quantum processors by 2016 and they increased the number to 16 qubits within a year (Santos, 2016). To this date, this remains an exciting opportunity for undergraduates, graduate students, and scientists to obtain hands-on experience to develop, run and simulate quantum algorithms through the IBM cloud-computing platform. The “IBMQ Commercial” program is responsible for providing quantum processors with a larger number of qubits, such as 20, 30, and 50 qubits, based on a commercial basis (Nay, 2019).

Figure 1-6 (Left) The quantum processor known as the “Eagle” is said to be the most powerful one that IBM possesses, which was introduced in 2021. The image is taken from (*IBM Unveils Breakthrough 127-Qubit Quantum Processor*, 2021). (Right) The actual look of a quantum computer, which requires a carefully controlled environment and conditions. The image is taken from (*IBM Q Experience Strives To Bring Quantum Computing To Masses - Quantum: Machine Learning & Analytics*, 2020)

IBM’s most powerful quantum device (known as the “Eagle” processor) was introduced in November 2021 with 127 qubits exceeding the 100-qubit mark, and it was a milestone in the

quantum computing industry (Chow, Dial and Gambetta, 2021). The number of qubits in a given quantum computer directly symbolizes the computational power within. IBM's quantum devices are said to be on a constant rise, whereas they previously introduced a 65-qubit quantum processor called "Hummingbird" in 2020 and a 27-qubit processor called "Falcon" in 2019 (Zhang *et al.*, 2020).

1.4 The significance of the study

The period that quantum devices are being developed consisting of 50-100 qubits is known as the NISQ (Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum) era (Preskill, 2018). This is exactly the time that we are passing at the moment. They have huge computing power, even at the developing stage. One of the key barriers for the NISQ devices is the noise present on the devices as previously explained. It is not guaranteed that the NISQ devices are meant to change the course of the world, but are considered a huge step toward advanced quantum devices in the future (Salm *et al.*, 2020).

Noise can be considered as the main limitation in the current devices, which negatively affects the results (Preskill, 2012). It also restricts the scalability of quantum devices. It is known that quantum error correction would be the key to solving the scalability problem in the NISQ devices to advance them further (Devitt, Munro and Nemoto, 2013). But on a contrary note, it comes with a huge cost and is expected not to be feasible soon. However, a thorough understanding of how the noise behaves and intervenes in the results at a fundamental level on real quantum hardware is important to pave the way for advanced and accurate quantum devices to be built in the future.

1.5 Objectives of the study

As previously pointed out, it is important to understand the conduct of noise and its impact on the final results within the NISQ devices. In this study, it is done with the aid of quantum search algorithms, by running them on simulators (theoretically expected results) and the actual quantum backends (experimental results) and comparing them to draw important conclusions. The specific objectives of the study are as follows.

- Implement Grover's algorithm on quantum simulators and currently available quantum processors for a higher number of qubits (3 and beyond) and analyze the errors.
- Attempt to minimize the occurrences of errors by applying error mitigation techniques (e.g.: by reducing the depth of the circuit).

- Implement the quantum random walk search algorithm and compare it with Grover's algorithm.

1.6 Outline of the thesis

The remainder of the thesis is organized as follows. Chapter 2 includes a literature survey regarding the evolution of quantum computing and quantum search algorithms. In chapter 3, theory related to quantum computing and the implementation of the Grover algorithm and quantum random walk search algorithm is presented. In chapter 4, the reader's attention is drawn toward the methodology followed in the research. Chapter 5 presents the results and an analysis of them. A detailed discussion regarding the obtained results is provided in chapter 6. Chapter 7 summarizes the important conclusions that can be drawn from this study.

2 BACKGROUND

Quantum computation can be regarded as an interdisciplinary field where quantum mechanics and computer science intersect together.

2.1 Evolution of quantum mechanics

The development of quantum mechanics spanned over the early period of the 20th century and was initiated when Max Planck explained blackbody radiation using quantum theory in 1900. (Boya, 2004). In 1905, another breakthrough took place when Albert Einstein suggested that electromagnetic radiation was quantized to explain the photoelectric effect (Arons and Peppard, 2005). Niels Bohr contributed to the advancement of quantum mechanics when in 1913 he used quantum theory to explain the structure of atoms (Bohr, 1913). In 1920, Louis de Broglie suggested that the particles also behave like waves (Weinberger, 2006). In 1925, Heisenberg introduced matrix mechanics which provided a mathematical foundation for quantum-mechanical concepts (Heisenberg, 1925). In 1926, Erwin Schrodinger proposed another mathematical formulation of quantum mechanics using wave mechanics, which fundamentally used the mathematical concept known as the “wave function” (Schrödinger, 1926). After the introduction of the theory of relativity by Einstein in 1915, Paul Dirac was able to successfully interconnect the concepts of quantum mechanics and the theory of special relativity in 1927 (Dirac and John, 1927). The uncertainty principle proposed by Heisenberg in 1925 was another milestone, where he suggested a limit for the precision of the simultaneous measurement of an observable and the time required to make the necessary measurements related to the observable (Heisenberg, 1925).

2.2 Evolution of computer science

In the early part of the 20th century, the development of computer science commenced. In 1936, Alan Turing proposed a solution to the Hilbert Entscheidungs problem with the construction of a formal model of a computer, which was later known as the “Turing Machine”. (Turing, 1936). The electromechanical computer known as “Mark I”, which was built at Harvard University with the aid of IBM in 1944, was the first step toward the development of an electronic digital computer (*IBM Archives: IBM’s ASCC (a.k.a. The Harvard Mark I)*). This was followed by numerous machines such as ENIAC, EDVAC, and EDSAC (*ENIAC - CHM Revolution*). The invention of the transistor by Bardeen, Barttain, and Shockley in 1947 immensely contributed to an accelerated revolution in the computing industry (Huff and Bardeen, 2001). The hardware related to computing took a sharp rise after that. Computer

science was then considered a separate discipline starting from the 1960s. More theoretical approaches were taken to introduce a rigorous mathematical formulation for algorithms with the work of Donald Knuth (*Knuth (Donald E.) Papers*).

2.3 Evolution of quantum computing

The incredible union between quantum physics and computer science was first introduced with the work of Yuri Manin in 1980 (*Yu. I. Manin, "Computable and Non-Computable," Sovetskoe Radio, Moscow, 1980, 128 p. - References - Scientific Research Publishing*). Similarly, Toffoli's idea of reversible computing was crucial at the initial stage of the development of the basic concepts (Toffoli, 1980). Paul Benioff's paper in 1982 regarding the quantum mechanical Hamiltonian models was a breakthrough, where he was able to model the time-dependent and time-independent Hamiltonian models, on a finite lattice of a spin-1/2 system (Benioff, 1982). Then in 1985, the famous physicist Richard Feynman, suggested that one should be able to reduce the size of computers, adhering to the laws of physics, until the quantum behavior begins to dominate (Feynman, 1985).

The development then started to advance around the basis of a digital platform, when David Deutsch proposed the postulation of a quantum computer that can be universally accepted, (Deutsch, 1985). In the same year Peres introduced the connection between reversible logic and quantum computers (Peres, 1985) Then in the following years, more people were involved in developing quantum algorithms to solve physical problems with an accelerated time. The first quantum algorithm was introduced by David Deutsch and R. Jozsa in 1992, which was later named the "Deutsch-Jozsa" algorithm (Deutsch and Jozsa, 1992). One of the key moments in the history of quantum computation was Peter Shor's paper on the polynomial-time algorithm for prime factorization and discrete logarithms, in 1994 (Peter *et al.*, 1994). It successfully drew much larger attention to the field, since these two problems were extremely computationally hard, and solving these problems, using a quantum computer would break modern-day public key encryption methods posing a significant threat to network and internet security.

Then in 1997, Daniel Simon was able to prove the higher complexity power of the quantum models when compared to the Probabilistic Turing Machines (Simon, 1997). The quantum complexity theory introduced by E. Bernstein and Umesh Vazirani in 1997 was also crucial in the development of quantum algorithms (Bernstein, and Vazirani, 1997).

2.4 History of quantum search algorithms

2.4.1 Grover's algorithm

In 1997, L.K Grover proposed a quantum algorithm for unstructured search which was later named the “Grover’s algorithm” (Grover, 1997). A database with N randomly placed items could be searched with $O(N)$ database accesses using classical search algorithms. But Grover proved that using the proposed quantum search algorithm, only $O(\sqrt{N})$ accesses are needed, which is in general a quadratic speed up. In 1998, Jones, Mosca, and Hansen experimentally proved that a quantum computer based on nuclear magnetic resonance, can be used to implement Grover’s algorithm (Jones, Mosca, and Hansen, 1998). It was the first time that Grover’s algorithm was justified experimentally.

In 1998, Chuang, Gershenfeld, and Kubinec successfully implemented Grover’s search algorithm on a quantum system consisting of four states, with the support of CHCl_3 molecules, by exploiting the idea of nuclear magnetic resonance (Chuang, Gershenfeld, and Kubinec, 1998). In 1999, Pablo-Norman and Altaba claimed that Grover’s algorithm loses efficiency in the presence of noise and it could slow down to the level of its classical counterpart depending on the amount of noise added to the circuit (Pablo-Norman and Ruiz-Altaba, 2000). In 1999, Vandersypen et al. experimentally implemented Grover’s search algorithm for three qubits (Vandersypen *et al.*, 1999). The investigated quantum computer consisted of CHFBr_2 molecules, and the qubits were three weakly-coupled nuclei. The measurements were read with the aid of nuclear magnetic resonance techniques.

In 2000, Zalka’s paper suggested that it is still possible to find a practical advantage of Grover’s algorithm for searching databases, by further analyzing and comparing the search based on classical theory and quantum theory (Zalka, 2000). One of the common applications of Grover’s algorithm is the Boolean Satisfiability problems. Implementation of Grover’s algorithm on quantum hardware had been the primary target for a long time and in 2013 M. Waseem et al. introduced an implementation for the three-qubit case (Waseem *et al.*, 2013). They successfully integrated a superconducting resonator for this task. This study proved that with the development of better quantum hardware, a higher fidelity could be achieved.

In 2016, Chakraborty and Maitra investigated the application of the algorithm to a Boolean function and the way that the quadratic improvement of the query complexity could be achieved using Grover’s technique (Chakraborty and Maitra, 2016). Mandviwalla’s approach showed that quantum computers are capable of solving problems where there is a lack of

available data, 2018 (Mandviwalla, Ohshiro, and Ji, 2019). Also, it was suggested that there are peculiar differences in the results when different qubits are selected. In 2020, Gilliam, Pistoia, and Gonciulea proposed that the “inversion about the mean” step in the algorithm could be optimized (Gilliam, Pistoia and Gonciulea, 2020). Theoretically, it led to a new interpretation of the “inversion about the mean” step, and experimentally it was shown that the performance was improved.

In 2020, Zhang and Korepin proposed the idea that the depth of the quantum circuit significantly affects the performance of quantum computers (Zhang and Korepin, 2020). They presented the idea that Grover’s algorithm could be implemented in several ways, optimizing the final results to reduce the errors. In 2021, Kun Zhang implemented Grover’s algorithm on IBM hardware and discussed the limitations of implementing Grover’s algorithm on near-term quantum hardware (Zhang *et al.*, 2021). In 2021, Karlsson and Strömberg claimed that due to the limitations in the current quantum hardware, the accuracy of the 4-qubit Grover implementation is not adequate. (Blomkvist Karlsson and Strömberg, 2018).

2.4.2 Quantum random walk search algorithm

In 2001, Childs *et al.* presented the general definition of a quantum random walk on a graph (Childs, Farhi, and Gutmann, 2001). In 2003 Childs *et al.* constructed an oracular problem and solved it faster with the quantum approach in contrast to the classical approach, by rapidly traversing a graph (Childs *et al.*, 2003).

In 2003, Neil Shenvi proposed a search algorithm based on quantum random walks (Shenvi, Kempe, and Whaley, 2003). It was proved to have a quadratic speed up, which is similar to Grover’s algorithm when performing database searches. In 2003 Andris Ambainis introduced the algorithmic applications of the quantum walk (Ambainis, 2003). He was successful in solving the following problems; quantum search on a hypercube, quantum search on a grid, and the element distinctness.

In 2009, Korepin and Xu’s paper on quantum search algorithms proposed the idea that even though the amplitude amplification technique used in both algorithms is similar, it is difficult to perceive a method to amplify the amplitude (Korepin and Xu, 2009). In 2009, Childs proposed that the quantum walk can be considered as a universal computational primitive, where quantum computations are encoded into a graph (Childs, 2009).

In 2015 Thomas Wong introduced the idea that even though the quantum walk transitions between vertices should happen with perfect fidelity, the particle can be constrained by potential energy barriers (Wong, 2015). He further suggested that the quantum error correction was vital in searching larger databases. In 2020, Thomas Wang discussed how random and quantum walks can be used to search spatial regions (Wong, 2020). In this case, the problem of finding a search item in a database was reformulated as a spatial search problem.

2.5 Evolution of quantum computing hardware

The development of quantum hardware has advanced immensely in the last decade, whereas many prominent tech companies such as Google, IBM, Amazon, etc. have entered the competition to achieve quantum supremacy. Sycamore processor consisting of 54 qubits from Google, and the Eagle processor by IBM are a few examples for currently available NISQ devices. In 2019, Google achieved the long-awaited milestone known as the “quantum computing supremacy” (Gibney, 2019). This proved that quantum computers are capable of surpassing classical computers. In other words, it meant that it is impossible for any classical computer to imitate what a quantum computer with 54 qubits can simulate (Powell, 2019). In addition to that, China has recently entered the competition with its new photonic quantum computer “Jiuzhang” (Choi, 2021). In 2021, IBM introduced their most powerful quantum processor known as “Eagle”, exceeding the 100-qubit limit, consisting of 127 qubits (Chow, Dial and Gambetta, 2021). They successfully used a new qubit lattice arrangement in this processor (Smith, 2021). Additionally, this confirmed that IBM is capable of scaling their quantum processors according to their “quantum computing roadmap”. Therefore, a steep rise in quantum computing technologies can be expected in the next decade as well.

3 THEORY

3.1 A concise review of linear algebra

3.1.1 Complex vectors

A vector with complex numbers can be identified as a complex vector. For example, $\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 - i \end{pmatrix}$ is a complex vector. In general, an arbitrary complex vector ($|\psi\rangle$) in the d-dimensional complex vector space (\mathbb{C}^d) is written as,

$$|\psi\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} \psi_1 \\ \psi_2 \\ \vdots \\ \psi_d \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where $\psi_i \in \mathbb{C}$.

The notation $|x\rangle$ is known as the Dirac notation which is a standard convention to represent column vectors. Complex vectors play a significant role in quantum mechanics since they represent quantum states. (Gharibian, 2015)

3.1.2 Inner product

The conjugate transpose of a complex vector $|\psi\rangle$ can be given as,

$$\langle\psi| = (\psi_1^* \quad \psi_2^* \quad \dots \quad \psi_d^*) \quad (2)$$

where ψ_i^* are the complex conjugates of ψ_i 's.

Given that the two complex vectors are ψ and ϕ , the inner product between them is defined as follows.

$$\langle\psi|\phi\rangle = \sum_{i=1}^d \psi_i^* \phi_i \quad (3)$$

With this knowledge, one can easily determine the magnitude of a complex vector by considering the overlap of that particular complex vector with itself.

3.1.3 Orthonormal bases

A set of vectors denoted by $\{|\psi_i\rangle\} \subseteq \mathbb{C}^d$ is regarded orthogonal if the following condition is satisfied.

$$\langle \psi_i | \psi_j \rangle = 0; \quad \text{when } i \neq j \quad (4)$$

The set of vectors is considered orthonormal if the following condition is satisfied,

$$\langle \psi_i | \psi_i \rangle = \delta_{ij} \quad (5)$$

where δ_{ij} represents the Kronecker delta function.

The general expansion for an arbitrary d-dimensional vector is defined as,

$$|\phi\rangle = \sum_{i=1}^d a_i |\psi_i\rangle \quad (6)$$

where $a_i = \langle \psi_i | \phi \rangle$.

3.1.4 Linear operators

An operator gives the notion that how a particular complex vector is transformed into another vector. By definition, a linear operator should satisfy the following condition for an operator $\hat{A}: C^d \rightarrow C^d$ and given that $\sum_{i=1}^d \alpha_i |\psi_i\rangle \in C^d$. (Gharibian, 2015)

$$\hat{A} \left(\sum_{i=1}^d \alpha_i |\psi_i\rangle \right) = \sum_{i=1}^d \alpha_i \phi(|\psi_i\rangle) \quad (7)$$

A linear operator can be represented in matrix form. This representation depends on the particular choice of basis vectors. Suppose that A is a $d \times d$ matrix. The previously defined linear operator $\phi: C^d \rightarrow C^d$ can be represented by matrix A as shown in Equation (8). Here, the i 'th column of A is given by $\hat{A}|\psi_i\rangle$, where $\{|\psi_i\rangle\}$ is the standard basis for C^d .

$$A = [\hat{A}|\psi_1\rangle \quad \hat{A}|\psi_2\rangle \quad \dots \quad \hat{A}|\psi_{d-1}\rangle] \quad (8)$$

3.1.5 Outer product

The outer product provides another representation of matrices with the aid of the Dirac notation as previously introduced in this section. It can be defined as $|\psi\rangle\langle\phi|$ where $|\psi\rangle, |\phi\rangle \in C^d$. The result of the outer product is a matrix, and in this case, it is a $d \times d$ matrix. For the two-dimensional complex vector space, the following outer product can be calculated using the matrix multiplication rules.

$$|\psi\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{pmatrix}, |\phi\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$|\psi\rangle\langle\phi| = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{pmatrix} (b_1 \quad b_2) = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 b_1 & a_1 b_2 \\ a_2 b_1 & a_2 b_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

3.2 Quantum mechanics of two-level systems

3.2.1 Qubit

Unlike in the classical world where a bit can have the value 0 or 1, the quantum bit can have both values 0 and 1 simultaneously, which is a counter-intuitive idea at first look. Assume that the classical bits 0 and 1 are represented by the standard basis vectors $|0\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$ and $|1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$, where $|0\rangle, |1\rangle \in \mathbb{C}^2$. Then the general state of a qubit can be expressed by,

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle, \quad (11)$$

where $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$.

It is known that the state $|\psi\rangle$ should be a unit vector. Therefore, the following is a necessary condition for the above statement to be true.

$$|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1 \quad (12)$$

3.2.2 Linear operations on qubits

The linear maps can be defined on qubits, which are represented by matrices. But it is known that only the unitary matrices are applicable, where a unitary matrix satisfies $UU^\dagger = U^\dagger U = 1$. In quantum computing terminology, a unitary operator is commonly referred to as a quantum gate. For example, the following quantum gates known as the Pauli gates are among the most common gates used in quantum computing.

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad Y = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & i \\ -i & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad Z = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

3.2.3 Multiple-qubit states and tensor product

The tensor product is needed to represent multiple qubits simultaneously, which is denoted by \otimes . It gives the notion of combining two vectors. Assuming that $|\psi\rangle, |\phi\rangle \in \mathbb{C}^2$, the four-dimensional vector $|\omega\rangle$, is given by the tensor product $|\psi\rangle \otimes |\phi\rangle \in \mathbb{C}^2 \times \mathbb{C}^2 = \mathbb{C}^4$. In general, the entries of a vector $|\psi\rangle \otimes |\phi\rangle \in \mathbb{C}^2 \times \mathbb{C}^2$ can be represented using a pair of indices (i, j)

for $i, j \in \{0,1\}$, per the following relationship where ψ_i and ϕ_j are the entries of $|\psi\rangle$ and $|\phi\rangle$. (Gharibian, 2015)

$$(|\psi\rangle \otimes |\phi\rangle)(i, j) = \psi_i \phi_j \quad (14)$$

For example, the first two entries of the quantum state $|\omega\rangle \in \mathbb{C}^2 \times \mathbb{C}^2 = \mathbb{C}^4$ can be represented as follows.

$$|0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Assuming that there are two orthonormal bases $A = \{|\psi_0\rangle, |\psi_1\rangle\}$ and $B = \{|\phi_0\rangle, |\phi_1\rangle\}$ for \mathbb{C}^2 , an orthonormal basis for \mathbb{C}^4 can be obtained by combining the elements in A and B , using the definition of tensors defined above as $\{|\psi_0\rangle \otimes |\phi_0\rangle, |\psi_0\rangle \otimes |\phi_1\rangle, |\psi_1\rangle \otimes |\phi_0\rangle, |\psi_1\rangle \otimes |\phi_1\rangle\}$. For a simple notation the tensor product $|\psi\rangle \otimes |\phi\rangle = |\psi\rangle|\phi\rangle$.

Assuming a system of two qubits with quantum states $|x\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} x_0 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix}$, $|y\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} y_0 \\ y_1 \end{bmatrix}$, the composite quantum state of the two-qubit system is realized in the following form.

$$|yx\rangle = |y\rangle \otimes |x\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} y_0 \times \begin{bmatrix} x_0 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix} \\ y_1 \times \begin{bmatrix} x_0 \\ x_1 \end{bmatrix} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} y_0 x_0 \\ y_0 x_1 \\ y_1 x_0 \\ y_1 x_1 \end{bmatrix}$$

3.3 Fundamentals in quantum computing

3.3.1 Circuit diagrams

Boolean circuits:

A collection of logic gates and inputs connected by wires can be defined as a Boolean circuit. Mainly a Boolean circuit consists of AND, OR, and NOT gates, and the usage of the gates depends on the type of the Boolean function defined for the circuit. The logic gates are the key components in any circuit diagram, which are different types of models of computations.

Quantum circuits:

A quantum circuit can be thought of as the quantum analogy of a Boolean circuit. A quantum circuit is formally defined as an ordered arrangement of quantum gates, measurements, and resets. (*Defining Quantum Circuits*, QISKIT)

Figure 3-1 (Left) An example of a normal Boolean circuit. The image is taken from (Kyang, 2018). (Right) An example of a simple quantum circuit drawn in QISKIT.

3.3.2 Visual representation of qubit states using Bloch sphere

Previously it was shown that the general quantum state of a qubit can be represented as $|\psi\rangle = a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle$ where $a, b \in \mathbb{C}$. It was noted that one cannot simply measure the global phase, but the phase difference between the states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$. By introducing $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{R}$, and $\phi \in [0, 2\pi]$, the general state of a qubit can be expressed as,

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + e^{i\phi}\beta|1\rangle$$

This satisfies the condition $\sqrt{\alpha^2 + \beta^2} = 1$, due to the normalization.

Using trigonometry, α and β could be written in terms of an angle θ as follows.

$$\alpha = \cos \frac{\theta}{2}, \beta = \sin \frac{\theta}{2}$$

Figure 3-2 The representation of a qubit using the Bloch sphere. The image is taken from (Warke, 2019)

This yields the following result, which represents the quantum state of any arbitrary qubit as,

$$|q\rangle = \cos \frac{\theta}{2}|0\rangle + e^{i\phi}\sin \frac{\theta}{2}|1\rangle$$

where $\theta \in [0, \pi]$, and $\phi \in [0, 2\pi]$.

By interpreting that θ and ϕ as spherical coordinates, any arbitrary single-qubit state could be portrayed on the surface of the sphere, known as the “Bloch Sphere”.

Figure 3-3 The Bloch sphere representation of the $|0\rangle$ state (first from left), $|1\rangle$ state (second from left), $|+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)$ state (third from left), and $|+i\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + i|1\rangle)$ state (fourth from left).

3.3.3 Single qubit gates

X gate

The X gate is capable of rotating the state of the qubit 180 degrees about the X-axis on the Bloch sphere. It is also referred as the bit flip gate. It is represented by the following matrix.

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = |0\rangle\langle 1| + |1\rangle\langle 0|$$

Y gate

The Y gate is capable of rotating the state of the qubit 180 degrees about the Y-axis on the Bloch sphere. It is represented by the following matrix.

$$Y = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{bmatrix} = -i|0\rangle\langle 1| + i|1\rangle\langle 0|$$

Z gate

The Z gate is capable of rotating the state of the qubit 180 degrees about the Z-axis. It is represented by the following matrix.

$$Z = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} = |0\rangle\langle 0| - |1\rangle\langle 1|$$

Figure 3-4 The application of an X gate rotates the qubit 180 degrees on the X-axis as shown in the Bloch sphere representation.

Hadamard gate

The Hadamard gate is used to create superpositions of $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ states. It mainly does the following mappings.

$$H|0\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle) = |+\rangle$$

$$H|1\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle - |1\rangle) = |-\rangle$$

The matrix representation of the Hadamard gate is in the following form.

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 3-5 (Left) The transformation of the state $|0\rangle$ to $|+\rangle$ is shown in the Bloch sphere representation. (Right) The transformation of the state $|1\rangle$ to $|-\rangle$ is shown using the Bloch sphere notation.

3.3.4 Multiple qubits and entangled states

As explained in section 3.2.3, the tensor product is the linear algebraic mathematical tool that is used to represent the composite quantum states of multiple qubits.

Single qubit gates on multi qubits

Consider a two-qubit system for which a Hadamard gate is applied to the 1st qubit (q_0) and an X gate is applied to the 2nd qubit (q_1) (see Figure 3-6). The tensor product can be applied to find the matrix representation of the corresponding composite operator.

Figure 3-6 A Hadamard gate and an X-gate are applied to the first and the second qubit respectively.

$$X \otimes H = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Multi qubit gates

CNOT gate

CNOT gate is one of the common multi-qubit gates used in quantum circuits. The main objective of this conditional gate is to apply an X-gate on the target qubit, given that the control qubit is in the $|1\rangle$ state.

Table 3-1 Classical truth table for the CNOT gate

Input (Target qubit, Control qubit)	Output (Target qubit, Control qubit)
00	00
01	11
10	10
11	01

The matrix representation of the CNOT gate is given by the following matrix.

$$\text{CNOT} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 3-7 Circuit representation of the CNOT gate. In this representation, q_0 is the control bit while q_1 is the target bit.

Q-sphere representation

Q sphere is mainly used for visualizing multiple-qubit states, and it provides information about the multi qubits and single qubits with their respective amplitudes and phase of the constituent basis states. The size of the blob is proportional to the amount of probability for a specific state, whereas the color represents its phase.

Q-sphere representation for the multi-qubit state $| - + \rangle = \frac{1}{2}(|00\rangle + |01\rangle - |10\rangle - |11\rangle)$ can be realized as shown in Figure 3-8.

Figure 3-8 The Q-sphere representation of the multi-qubit state $| - + \rangle = \frac{1}{2}(|00\rangle + |01\rangle - |10\rangle - |11\rangle)$. Note that $|10\rangle$ and $|11\rangle$ states have a phase difference of π , shown as yellow blobs.

3.4 Grover’s algorithm

The primary objective of Grover’s algorithm is solving search problems. Consider a situation where only one of the elements satisfies a certain condition in an unsorted list of N elements. In the worst-case scenario, $O(N)$ queries to the list should be made by any classical algorithm. But Grover’s algorithm can find the element with $O(\sqrt{N})$ queries made to the list, which is a quadratic speedup. This speedup can be recognized as a time saver when searching large databases which reflects the immense significance of Grover’s algorithm.

3.4.1 The oracle

The oracle can be considered as a “black box” in general, that can recognize the solutions to the search problem.

Assume that the search space consists of N elements, and each element is indexed by an integer from 0 to $N - 1$. Suppose that $N = 2^n$ for the convenience where n is the number of bits, and there are M number of solutions for the particular search problem where $1 \leq M \leq N$.

At a given time, the search problem can be represented with the aid of the following function f which takes an integer argument x in the range of 0 to $N - 1$. (Vazirani, 2007)

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 1; & \text{if } x \text{ is a solution to the search problem} \\ 0; & \text{if } x \text{ is not a solution to the search problem} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

It is assumed that the oracle is capable of recognizing the solutions to the search problem with the support of a qubit which is known as the oracle qubit ("q"). The oracle can be interpreted as a unitary operator defined as follows, on the computational basis where $|x\rangle$ represents the index register and \oplus symbolizes the addition modulo 2 operations.

$$|x\rangle|q\rangle \xrightarrow{\text{Oracle}} |x\rangle|q \oplus f(x)\rangle \quad (16)$$

Here, the oracle qubit "q" is flipped if $f(x) = 1$ and unaltered otherwise. In the simplest terms, one can prepare the combined state $|x\rangle|0\rangle$ in the beginning, followed by an oracle to check whether x is a solution to the search problem. Therefore, if the oracle qubit is measured to be $|1\rangle$, then $|x\rangle$ is a solution.

Figure 3-9 The general oracle can be defined as shown in the figure. If the oracle qubit is measured to be $|1\rangle$, then $|x\rangle$ is a solution to the search problem.

It is accepted that the initialization of the oracle qubit, to the state $\frac{|0\rangle - |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ (also known as the $|-\rangle$ state) is beneficial for the later stage implementations. Then the application of the oracle performs the following to the combined quantum state.

$$|x\rangle \left(\frac{|0\rangle - |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \xrightarrow{\text{Oracle}} \begin{cases} -|x\rangle \left(\frac{|0\rangle - |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right); & \text{if } x \text{ is a solution to the search problem} \\ |x\rangle \left(\frac{|0\rangle - |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right); & \text{if } x \text{ is not a solution to the search problem} \end{cases}$$

This action of the oracle could be summarized as follows.

$$|x\rangle \left(\frac{|0\rangle - |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \xrightarrow{\text{Oracle}} (-1)^{f(x)} |x\rangle \left(\frac{|0\rangle - |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \quad (17)$$

or equivalently,

$$|x\rangle |-\rangle \xrightarrow{\text{Oracle}} (-1)^{f(x)} |x\rangle |-\rangle \quad (18)$$

Note that according to the above relationship, the state of the oracle qubit remains unaltered. Therefore, the action of the oracle of Grover's algorithm can be expressed in the most simplified manner as follows.

$$|x\rangle \xrightarrow{\text{Oracle}} (-1)^{f(x)} |x\rangle \quad (19)$$

This action is known as the "phase inversion". The matrix representation of the oracle (say "O") can be given as follows.

$$O = \begin{bmatrix} (-1)^{f(0)} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & (-1)^{f(1)} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & 0 & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & (-1)^{f(2^n-1)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

Figure 3-10 The action of the oracle in Grover's algorithm is expressed using quantum circuit notation. Here, the oracle qubit is initialized to the $|-\rangle$ state. The state of the oracle qubit remains unchanged throughout the process.

3.4.2 The algorithmic procedure

To gain the best performance for the task of finding the desired search item, the algorithm should be capable of finding the search element with the least number of oracle applications.

At the beginning of the algorithm, the computer starts at the state of $|0\rangle^{\otimes n}$. Then all the qubits are put into a state of equal superposition using Hadamard transformations. This equal superposition state can be expressed as follows. (Vazirani, 2007)

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{x=0}^{N-1} |x\rangle \quad (21)$$

Then again, Hadamard transformations are applied to each qubit, followed by an application of a phase shift of -1 for every computational basis state except state $|0\rangle$. Then Hadamard transformations are reapplied to the qubits. This collective operation is known as the diffusion operation. The operator responsible for this task can be recognized as $2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| - I$ in the following way.

$$\begin{aligned} H^{\otimes n} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & \dots & 0 \\ \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} H^{\otimes n} &= H^{\otimes n} \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} - I \right\} H^{\otimes n} \\ H^{\otimes n} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \dots & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} H^{\otimes n} - H^{\otimes n} I H^{\otimes n} &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2}{N} & \frac{2}{N} & \dots & \frac{2}{N} \\ \frac{2}{N} & \frac{2}{N} & \dots & \frac{2}{N} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \frac{2}{N} & \frac{2}{N} & \dots & \frac{2}{N} \end{bmatrix} - I \\ &= 2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| - I \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

It can be shown that when the diffusion operation is applied to an arbitrary superposition state $\sum_k \alpha_k |k\rangle$, it gives $\sum_k [-\alpha_k + 2\langle\alpha\rangle] |k\rangle$, where $\langle\alpha\rangle = \frac{\sum_k \alpha_k |k\rangle}{N}$ is the mean value of α_k (Nielsen and Chuang, 2011). Hence, the operation of $(2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| - I)$ is also known as the process of “inversion of the mean”.

The complete Grover operation can be expressed as $G = (2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| - I)O$, where O represents the oracle.

Figure 3-11 The complete Grover circuit consisting of the oracle followed by the diffusion operator. Here, $H^{\otimes n}$ represents the Hadamard transform, U_f represents the oracle, and $U_{\neq 0^n}$ represents the phase shift operation.

3.5 Geometric interpretation of Grover's algorithm

As the first step, the initial state vector $|\psi\rangle$ can be recognized as shown in the following expression.

$$|\psi\rangle = \sqrt{\frac{N-M}{M}} |\alpha\rangle + \sqrt{\frac{M}{N}} |\beta\rangle \quad (22)$$

Here, N is the total number of search items and M is the number of solutions. $|\alpha\rangle$ is a combined state of all x which are not solutions to the search problem and $|\beta\rangle$ state represents all the states x' which are solutions, where $|\alpha\rangle$ and $|\beta\rangle$ states can be defined as follows.

$$|\alpha\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N-M}} \sum_x |x\rangle \quad (23)$$

$$|\beta\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{M}} \sum_{x'} |x'\rangle \quad (24)$$

The complete Grover iteration can be interpreted as a combination of a reflection and a rotation in the complex vector space as illustrated in Figure 3-12.

Figure 3-12 The complex vector space spanned by the $|\alpha\rangle$ and $|\beta\rangle$ states which are orthonormal, exposing the complete solution space. The initial state $|\psi\rangle$ makes an angle of $\frac{\theta}{2}$ with $|\alpha\rangle$. The $|\psi\rangle$ state is reflected about the state $|\alpha\rangle$ by the oracle operation where $O|\psi\rangle$ represents the consequent state. After that, $O|\psi\rangle$ state is again reflected about $|\psi\rangle$, where the consequent state is represented by $G|\psi\rangle$. After the two consecutive reflections, the initial state $|\psi\rangle$ now have been rotated toward the state $|\beta\rangle$ by an angle θ . The image is taken from (Nielsen and Chuang, 2011).

Figure 3-12 represents the complex vector space spanned by the two orthonormal states $|\alpha\rangle$ and $|\beta\rangle$. As the first step, the initial state $|\psi\rangle = p|\alpha\rangle + q|\beta\rangle$ is reflected about the vector $|\alpha\rangle$ by the Oracle operation shown in the following expression.

$$O|\psi\rangle = O(p|\alpha\rangle + q|\beta\rangle) = p|\alpha\rangle - q|\beta\rangle; p, q \in \mathbb{C} \quad (25)$$

Then the operation $2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| - I$, again performs a reflection of the state $O|\psi\rangle$ about the state $|\psi\rangle$. Since the product of two reflections is equivalent to a rotation, the initial state $|\psi\rangle$ now has been rotated towards the orthonormal state $|\beta\rangle$ by an angle θ in the above figure. The effect of a single Grover's iteration on the initial state $|\psi\rangle$ can be expressed by,

$$G|\psi\rangle = \cos\left(\frac{3\theta}{2}\right)|\alpha\rangle + \sin\left(\frac{3\theta}{2}\right)|\beta\rangle \quad (26)$$

where

$$|\psi\rangle = \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)|\alpha\rangle + \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)|\beta\rangle; \quad (27)$$

with

$$\sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) = \sqrt{\frac{M}{N}}, \quad \text{and} \quad \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) = \sqrt{\frac{N-M}{M}}. \quad (28)$$

Repeated application of the Grover iteration (G) on the initial state $|\psi\rangle$ over a number of times yields the following state.

$$G^n|\psi\rangle = \cos\left(\frac{[2n+1]\theta}{2}\right)|\alpha\rangle + \sin\left(\frac{[2n+1]\theta}{2}\right)|\beta\rangle \quad (29)$$

According to the above equation, one single Grover iteration rotates the state $|\psi\rangle$, towards the state $|\beta\rangle$ by θ radians. Repeated Grover iterations should theoretically bring the state $|\psi\rangle$ very close to the state $|\beta\rangle$, which results in a higher probability outcome for the state $|\beta\rangle$ when a measurement in the computational basis is performed. It is indeed the solution to the proposed search problem.

3.5.1 The optimal number of Grover iterations to a search problem

Consider the below figure, where the initial state $|\psi\rangle$ is defined in the complex vector space spanned by $|\alpha\rangle$ and $|\beta\rangle$.

Figure 3-13 The initial state $|\psi\rangle$ is defined in the complex vector space spanned by $|\alpha\rangle$ and $|\beta\rangle$.

Since, $\frac{\theta}{2} = \sin^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{M}{N}}$ according to the previously defined notation, an expression for ϕ can be determined using geometry as,

$$\phi = \cos^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{M}{N}} \quad (30)$$

Since a single Grover iteration rotates the state $|\psi\rangle$ towards $|\beta\rangle$ by an angle θ , to obtain the optimal result Grover operation should be repeated K times where K is defined as follows.

$$K = \frac{\cos^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{M}{N}}}{\theta} \quad (31)$$

Note that K should be approximated to the closest integer.

3.5.2 The limit to the number of iterations needed

A simple condition to yield an upper bound for the number of iterations can be introduced as follows. Since the angle between $|\alpha\rangle$ and $|\beta\rangle$ is $\frac{\pi}{2}$, the following condition should always be satisfied for the repetitions of the Grover iterations to be meaningful.

$$\phi \leq \frac{\pi}{2} \quad (32)$$

Dividing both sides by θ and substituting K for $\frac{\phi}{\theta}$, the following relationship can be realized.

$$K \leq \frac{\pi}{2\theta} \quad (33)$$

Assume that $M \leq \frac{N}{2}$ where M is the total number of solutions and N is the total number of search items. Then the following expression can be written.

$$\frac{\theta}{2} \geq \sin \frac{\theta}{2} = \sqrt{\frac{M}{N}} \quad (34)$$

This yields the following inequality.

$$\theta \geq 2\sqrt{\frac{M}{N}} \quad (35)$$

The inequalities (33) and (35) can be simplified in the following way.

$$K \leq \frac{\pi}{2\theta} \leq \frac{\pi}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{N}{M}} = \frac{\pi}{4} \sqrt{\frac{N}{M}} \quad (36)$$

Therefore,

$$K \leq \frac{\pi}{4} \sqrt{\frac{N}{M}} \quad (37)$$

As a result, the upper bound on the number of Grover iterations is $\frac{\pi}{4} \sqrt{\frac{N}{M}}$.

3.5.3 The effect of running Grover's algorithm for more than the optimal number of iterations

Consider the 2-qubit Grover's algorithm where only one search item is sought. In this case, $M = 1$ and $N = 2^2 = 4$. This yields the upper bound to be $\frac{\pi}{4} \sqrt{\frac{4}{1}} = 1.57$ which has the integer value equal to 1. This suggests that only one iteration is enough to find the search item.

Suppose that we want to find the search item $|00\rangle$. Then the initial state can be written in the following way.

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} |\alpha\rangle + \frac{1}{2} |\beta\rangle,$$

such that, $|\alpha\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}(|01\rangle + |10\rangle + |11\rangle)$ and $|\beta\rangle = |00\rangle$.

Comparing with the equation (28), it is clear that $\sin \frac{\theta}{2} = \frac{1}{2}$ which yields $\theta = \frac{\pi}{3}$. Now let's see what happens when a single Grover iteration is applied to the initial state $|\psi\rangle$.

According to equation (29),

$$G^1|\psi\rangle = \cos\left(\frac{3\theta}{2}\right) |\alpha\rangle + \sin\left(\frac{3\theta}{2}\right) |\beta\rangle$$

But since $\theta = \frac{\pi}{3}$, it follows that $\frac{3\theta}{2} = \frac{\pi}{2}$.

As a result,

$$G^1|\psi\rangle = 0|\alpha\rangle + 1|\beta\rangle$$

It means that after one iteration, we are capable of finding the desired search item with 100% probability.

It is interesting to see what happens when we go for 2 iterations continuously.

Then according to equation (29),

$$G^2|\psi\rangle = \cos\left(\frac{5\theta}{2}\right) |\alpha\rangle + \sin\left(\frac{5\theta}{2}\right) |\beta\rangle$$

But since $\theta = \frac{\pi}{3}$, it follows that $\frac{5\theta}{2} = \frac{5\pi}{6}$.

As a result,

$$G^2|\psi\rangle = -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}|\alpha\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|\beta\rangle$$

which yields,

$$G^2|\psi\rangle = -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}(|01\rangle + |10\rangle + |11\rangle)\right) + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1}}(|00\rangle)\right)$$

This can be simplified into the following relationship.

$$G^2|\psi\rangle = -\frac{1}{2}((|01\rangle + |10\rangle + |11\rangle)) + \frac{1}{2}(|00\rangle)$$

Per the above equation, each basis state (and therefore, each item) has a probability of 25% of being measured.

This concludes the idea that even though one can repeat the number of Grover iterations in a search problem above the optimal number of iterations, it would not guarantee better results. The results get worsened after crossing the upper bound (optimal number).

3.6 Quantum random walk search algorithm

3.6.1 Classical random walk

A random walk is a random process where a walker moves randomly through a path in random steps in a mathematical space. The simplest random walk is a 1-dimensional walk, where the walker moves on a numbered line. It is accepted that random walks are found in nature frequently, such as gas particles bouncing around in a container. The time it takes for the particle to move to one place from another depends on the particular system. Random walks take place in two-dimensional and three-dimensional spaces as well. Although most of the random walks allow the walker to move with equal probability in any arbitrary direction, some walks are biased in some specific direction.

3.6.2 Quantum walk

A Quantum Walk can be recognized as the quantum equivalent of the classical random walk. Unlike in a classical walk, where the next state is determined probabilistically, a quantum walk considers all the possible paths simultaneously in the fashion of superposition. Quantum walk algorithms are faster than their classical counterparts, due to the fact that one can exploit the quantum phenomenon of interference to get rid of some of the unwanted quantum states. The coined quantum walk is one of the most commonly used models to implement a quantum walk.

3.6.3 The coined quantum walks

Suppose that the quantum state of the coin (known as the coin state) belongs to \mathcal{H}_C and the quantum state of the position (known as the position state) belongs to \mathcal{H}_P , where \mathcal{H}_C and \mathcal{H}_P are the Hilbert spaces associated. Then the entire quantum space corresponding to the quantum walker is given by $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_C \otimes \mathcal{H}_P$.

3.6.4 Coin operator

In a classical random walk, a coin is flipped for each iteration on a graph, followed by the movement towards an adjacent node as determined by the outcome of the previously flipped coin. However, in a quantum walk, since the coin is a quantum coin, the following movements are in a state of superposition. In other words, it walks all possible paths simultaneously.

The Hadamard coin can be used in order to put a walker in a state of equal superposition, which is simply given by the Hadamard gate.

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (38)$$

In order to put a walker in a state of superposition with unequal probability amplitudes, one can use the Grover coin, which is simply the Grover diffusion operator denoted by the following matrix. In the Grover coin, there is a higher probability of being in the previous position than moving an adjacent node. In other words, the Grover coin is a biased coin.

$$G = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2}{n} - 1 & \frac{2}{n} & \dots & \frac{2}{n} \\ \frac{2}{n} & \frac{2}{n} - 1 & \dots & \frac{2}{n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{2}{n} & \frac{2}{n} & \dots & \frac{2}{n} - 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (39)$$

3.6.5 The shift operator (S)

This operator is responsible for moving the walker to the next position where $S \in \mathcal{H}_p$. For the case of 2D square, suppose that the walker is positioned at the state $|2\rangle$ as shown in Figure 3-14.

Figure 3-14 The walker is stationed at the state $|2\rangle$ (as shown by the red dot), and depending on the outcome of the coin, it can move to the state $|1\rangle$ or state $|3\rangle$.

One can define the movement of the walker with respect to the outcome of the coin as follows.

$$S |0\rangle|2\rangle = |0\rangle|1\rangle \quad (40)$$

$$S |1\rangle|2\rangle = |1\rangle|3\rangle \quad (41)$$

According to the above expressions, the complete evolution operator (W) of the quantum random walk, where S is the shift operator and C is the coin operator is given by,

$$W = S.C \quad (42)$$

3.6.6 Quantum walk search algorithm

The objective of this algorithm is to locate a marked vertex (or multiple such vertices) out of all the vertices in a given graph. The problem is solved in the form of a quantum walk.

Suppose that the quantum walk is defined based on a classical Markov chain (Magniez *et al.*, 2006). Then the transition matrix P is defined on the unitary operation $W(P)$ on \mathcal{H} . Note that, the set of marked vertices is denoted by M .

Assume that the current quantum state of an arbitrary node is $|x\rangle$ and its neighbors are represented as $|y\rangle$. Then the uniform superposition of the neighbors of the given node can be represented as follows, where $|x\rangle|y\rangle$ form a basis state.

$$|p_x\rangle = \sum_y \sqrt{P_{xy}}|y\rangle \quad (43)$$

Here, the behavior of $\sqrt{P_{xy}}$ is defined by the coin operator.

One can define the composite quantum state either as a combination of two spatial quantum states or as a combination of the spatial state and the coin state. Considering the former, the composite state $|x\rangle|y\rangle$ can be transformed into $|x\rangle|p_x\rangle$ given that the next state is a superposition state.

Following the same strategy used in Grover's algorithm the quantum state $|G\rangle$ is defined as the superposition state of all the marked nodes. Similarly, the quantum state $|B\rangle$ is defined for the remaining (unmarked) states.

$$|G\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{|M|}} \sum_{x \in M} |x\rangle |p_x\rangle, \quad (44)$$

$$|B\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N-|M|}} \sum_{x \notin M} |x\rangle |p_x\rangle, \quad (45)$$

Suppose that $\epsilon = \frac{|M|}{N}$ and $\theta = \sin^{-1}(\sqrt{\epsilon})$.

The uniform superposition of all the nodes can be represented as the following initial state.

$$|U\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_x |x\rangle |p_x\rangle = \sin \theta |G\rangle + \cos \theta |B\rangle \quad (46)$$

This can be achieved using a series of Hadamard gates.

Following the same technique used in Grover's algorithm, the complex amplitude of the marked search item in $|G\rangle$ can be amplified by reflecting the initial superposition state $|U\rangle$ over $|B\rangle$ followed by another reflection over $|U\rangle$.

After the reflection over $|B\rangle$, the resultant state $|U'\rangle$ can be represented as follows.

$$|U'\rangle = -\sin \theta |G\rangle + \cos \theta |B\rangle \quad (47)$$

This can be implemented using a phase oracle, similar to the one used in Grover's algorithm.

The state $|U'\rangle$ can be introduced as a superposition of state $|U\rangle$ and $|U^\perp\rangle$ as shown below.

$$|U'\rangle = \alpha |U\rangle + \beta |U^\perp\rangle \quad (48)$$

Figure 3-15 The operation of the phase oracle. The state $|U'\rangle$ is a superposition of states $|U\rangle$ and $|U^\perp\rangle$. The phase oracle reflects the state $|U'\rangle$ about $|U\rangle$ according to the linear mapping given in equations (49) and (50).

The reflection about $|U\rangle$ is a unitary operation that performs the following mapping.

$$|U\rangle \mapsto |U\rangle \quad (49)$$

$$|U^\perp\rangle \mapsto -|U^\perp\rangle \quad (50)$$

It is known that the evolution operator $W(P)$ has an eigenvector $|U\rangle$ with a corresponding eigenvalue of 1.

$$W(P)|U\rangle = 1 \cdot |U\rangle \quad (51)$$

Generally, for an arbitrary vector $|V\rangle$,

$$W(P)|V\rangle = e^{2\pi\theta i}|V\rangle \quad (52)$$

The angle θ can be measured using the popular quantum algorithm known as Quantum Phase Estimation (see section 3.6.7). Depending on the value of theta, one of the following actions is taken.

Case 1:

If $\theta = 0$, then the eigenvalue is 1, and therefore $|V\rangle = |U\rangle$. Therefore, the corresponding state $|U\rangle$ is kept as it is.

Case 2:

If $\theta \neq 0$, then the eigenvalue is not equal to 1, and therefore $|V\rangle \neq |U\rangle$. Therefore, the corresponding state $|U^\perp\rangle$ is flipped with a phase of π .

3.6.7 Quantum phase estimation (QPE)

Quantum phase estimation (QPE) is a major component of the quantum random walk search algorithm (Shenvi, Kempe and Whaley, 2003). Suppose that an eigenvector $|\psi\rangle$ has its corresponding eigenvalue of $e^{i\theta\psi}$ for a given unitary operator U . The QPE algorithm is capable of extracting the angle θ_ψ , given the ability to prepare the eigenstate $|\psi\rangle$ (Kang and Asfaw, 2020).

$$U|\psi\rangle = e^{i\theta\psi}|\psi\rangle \quad (53)$$

Consider the circuit shown in Figure 3-16.

Figure 3-16 A high-level circuit diagram illustrating the quantum phase estimation algorithm.

The composite quantum state at each step of the circuit can be realized as follows.

$$|\psi_0\rangle = |0\rangle^{\otimes n} \otimes |\psi\rangle$$

$$|\psi_1\rangle = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}[|0\rangle + |1\rangle]\right)^{\otimes n} \otimes |\psi\rangle = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^n (|0\rangle + |1\rangle)^{\otimes n} \otimes |\psi\rangle$$

But observe that, $U^{2^x}|\psi\rangle = U^{2^{x-1}}U|\psi\rangle = U^{2^{x-2}}U(e^{i\theta_\psi}|\psi\rangle) = e^{i\theta_\psi}e^{i\theta_\psi}U^{2^{x-2}}|\psi\rangle = \dots = e^{i\theta_\psi 2^x}|\psi\rangle$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi_n\rangle &= \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^n (|0\rangle + e^{i\theta_\psi 2^{n-1}}|1\rangle) \otimes (|0\rangle \\ &\quad + e^{i\theta_\psi 2^{n-2}}|1\rangle) \otimes \dots \otimes (|0\rangle + e^{i\theta_\psi 2^1}|1\rangle) \otimes (|0\rangle \\ &\quad + e^{i\theta_\psi 2^0}|1\rangle) |\psi\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

Note that the quantum Fourier transform of an arbitrary n-qubit state is given by the following equation (Nielsen and Chuang, 2011).

$$\begin{aligned} |\tilde{x}\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^n}} \left(|0\rangle + e^{\frac{2\pi i x}{2^1}} |1\rangle \right) \otimes \left(|0\rangle + e^{\frac{2\pi i x}{2^2}} |1\rangle \right) \otimes \left(|0\rangle \right. \\ &\quad \left. + e^{\frac{2\pi i x}{2^3}} |1\rangle \right) \otimes \dots \otimes \left(|0\rangle + e^{\frac{2\pi i x}{2^n}} |1\rangle \right) \end{aligned} \quad (55)$$

After replacing x with $2^n \theta_\psi$, the state $|2^n \theta_\psi\rangle$ can be recovered by applying an inverse Fourier transform (Asfaw, 2020).

Figure 3-17 The complete circuit for quantum phase estimation, including the inverse QFT (Quantum Fourier Transform) operation.

Therefore,

$$|\psi_{final}\rangle = |2^n \theta\rangle \otimes |\psi\rangle \quad (56)$$

Finally, a measurement of the first quantum register yields an estimate of the phase angle. Since θ_ψ is multiplied by a pre-factor 2^n in the final state, θ_ψ can be measured with a precision of n bits (Kang and Asfaw, 2020).

4 METHODOLOGY

4.1 IBM cloud-based platform for quantum computing

IBM provides a cloud-based online platform for quantum computing in which the users can build their own quantum algorithms, simulate them and observe the results. It consists of “IBM Quantum Composer” and “IBM Quantum Lab”. IBM Quantum Composer provides the ability to develop quantum algorithms, and simulate quantum experiments. Users can utilize IBM Quantum Lab to program quantum circuits using QISKIT (see section 4.1.1) and run them on actual quantum processors and simulators. This study is based on this platform together with the QISKIT library.

IBM Quantum provides free open access to a few selected backends with different structures. Some of the high-end quantum processors with a higher number of qubits are only provided on a commercial basis. The maximum number of qubits on the freely available quantum devices has been limited to 5. For the first part of this study, the availability of 5 qubit quantum backends was adequate. But in order to observe the experimental results for the quantum random walk search algorithm, access to a quantum processor with at least 10 qubits was needed. However, this was not possible due to the 5-qubit limit of freely available quantum processors. `ibmq_belem`, `ibmq_santiago`, `ibmq_mumbai`, and `ibmq_toronto` can be recognized as a few openly accessible quantum processors.

Figure 4-1 The graphical user interface of the IBM cloud-computing platform provides up-to-date details about the quantum backends available for running quantum algorithms written by the users. Details of four backends are shown: `ibmq_nairobi`, `ibmq_jakarta`, `ibmq_quito`, and `ibmq_belem`.

4.1.1 QISKIT package

QISKIT (also known as the “Quantum Information Software Kit”), is a Python-based open-source software development kit with different features, specifically designed to work with quantum computers and develop quantum algorithms. The tools available in QISKIT can be utilized to create, develop, and manipulate different quantum algorithms and corresponding quantum circuits. In addition, it allows running the algorithms on quantum devices publicly and commercially available on the IBM cloud-based platform. IBM also provides access to quantum simulators through the cloud, which can also be installed on the local computer. In a more general sense, QISKIT can be recognized as a collection of software packages used to develop quantum programs and successfully guide them to different backends, in addition to running them on quantum simulators and real quantum hardware.

Figure 4-2 An example quantum circuit constructed using the QISKIT package. Using tools available in QISKIT, the circuit can be directly executed on IBM quantum processors or simulators.

4.1.2 QISKIT Aer simulator

The Aer simulator is a high-performance quantum simulator for executing quantum circuits constructed using QISKIT.

It allows users to test their quantum algorithms in an ideal setting, without being subjected to the limitations in the current NISQ (Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum) devices such as the noise and the limited number of qubits. The Aer simulator also allows one to incorporate highly accurate noise models, mimicking the behavior of actual, noisy quantum processors.

4.2 Selecting the most appropriate quantum backend for the study

Different Backends have different noise and different structures. More specifically, the noise in a quantum computer is different between the qubits, and between different types of gates. Therefore, choosing the correct backend for executing quantum circuits is a difficult task, but a very significant one. There are mainly two types of errors in a given quantum computing backend available on the cloud. These occur due to quantum decoherence and are characterized by relaxation time (T_1) and dephasing time (T_2).

Relaxation time (T1)

Due to quantum decoherence, a qubit in the excited state $|1\rangle$ swiftly relaxes to the ground state $|0\rangle$. This time is referred as relaxation time (T1). It represents the idea of how long a qubit remains in the excited state before it decays back to the ground state. In other words, only during this period, one can perform different actions on the qubit.

Dephasing time (T2)

A qubit in state $|+\rangle$ tends to change to the state $|-\rangle$ or vice versa, due to quantum decoherence. It results in a loss of phase information about the designated qubit. As a general rule of thumb, the runtime of a quantum circuit should not exceed the dephasing time. If it happens, then the quality of the readout data would be less accurate.

Available quantum backends

For the analysis of this study, mainly the `ibmq_belem` quantum backend was employed, fundamentally due to its lower error rates. Other than that, `ibmq_santiago` was also used for comparison purposes.

`ibmq_belem` quantum backend

As previously mentioned, this was the main backend used in this analysis. This backend consists of 5 qubits and is equipped with a Falcon r4T quantum processor. The basic gates used in the backend are the CNOT gate, Identity gate (ID), Z-axis Rotation gate (RZ), Square root gate (SX), and NOT gate (X). It has an average relaxation time of $94.32 \mu\text{s}$ and an average dephasing time of $114.62 \mu\text{s}$ (*IBM Quantum*).

`ibmq_santiago` quantum backend

This backend occupies a Falcon r4L quantum processor, with the CNOT gate, Identity gate (ID), Z-axis Rotation gate (RZ), Square root gate (SX), and NOT gate (X) as the basis gates of the backend. It has an average relaxation time of $122.39 \mu\text{s}$ and an average dephasing time of $43.38 \mu\text{s}$ (*IBM Quantum*).

ibmq_belem Error Map

ibmq_santiago Error Map

Figure 4-3 The error maps of the `ibmq_belem` (top) and `ibmq_santiago` (bottom) backends, which show the respective qubit-connectivity graphs and the error rates related to the backends.

4.3 Construction of the Grover’s algorithm

4.3.1 Creating the oracle circuit

Normally, the oracle is considered a “black box”, which has the designated objective of inverting the phase of the correct search item, when a set of items are fed into it. Similarly, the other items should be left alone. In other words, the function of the oracle is to identify a particular answer from an arbitrary set of items.

This means that we need to set up a “phase kickback” circuit for the oracle where only the correct search item gets a phase inversion but not others. A simple circuit for the two-qubit situation can be implemented by following the steps given below.

The construction of a CZ gate from a CNOT gate

CNOT gate applies an X operation to its target qubit when its control qubit is in the $|1\rangle$ state. Following the same logic, the controlled-Z gate of the CZ gate applies a Z operation to its target qubit when its control qubit is in the $|1\rangle$ state.

It is clear that the effect of the Z gate on the states $|+\rangle$, and $|-\rangle$ is similar to the effect of the X gate on the states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$. Also, we know that the Hadamard gate is capable of transforming the $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ states to $|+\rangle$ and $|-\rangle$, respectively. Therefore, it can be proved that the Z gate can be decomposed into two Hadamard gates and a single X gate as follows.

$$H X H = Z \tag{57}$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \tag{58}$$

This same procedure can be extended to design a CZ gate using a CNOT gate, which can be realized as follows.

$$H(CX)H = CZ \tag{59}$$

Figure 4-4 A CZ gate can be created by sandwiching a CNOT gate between two Hadamard gates.

4.3.2 The complete oracle circuit

The action of the Z gate on the basis states is as follows.

$$Z|0\rangle = |0\rangle, Z|1\rangle = -|1\rangle \quad (60)$$

Now consider the circuit shown in Figure 4-5, where $|00\rangle$ state is considered as the search element.

Figure 4-5 The oracle circuit for the 2-qubit case assuming that the state $|00\rangle$ is the search item.

The first qubit (q_0) is the control qubit, which is later transformed into state $|1\rangle$ using an X gate applied on the initial state of $|0\rangle$. Then the second qubit (q_1) is changed into state $|1\rangle$ as well, using another X gate. Since the control qubit of the CZ gate is in state $|1\rangle$, it changes the target qubit into $-|1\rangle$. That is, q_1 has now a phase angle of π . As a result, the search item $|00\rangle$ has now been marked. Finally, X gates are applied to both q_0 and q_1 to reverse the changes made to those qubits, while keeping the phase change intact. As a result of this operation, q_0 is now in the state of $|0\rangle$ and q_1 is in the state $-|0\rangle$. Therefore, collectively, the initial state of $|00\rangle$ has now been changed into $-|00\rangle$.

The matrix representation of the oracle O can be expressed as follows.

$$O = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (61)$$

The oracle has to be designed uniquely and it depends on the search item that needs to be sought. However, the general idea of constructing the CZ gate and using it remains the same. For a higher number of qubits, a multi-controlled CZ gate has to be implemented. Extending the same theory, it can be achieved with the aid of two Hadamard gates and a multi-controlled CX gate.

Figure 4-6 The 3-qubit oracle circuit for finding the search item $|001\rangle$.

Figure 4-6 shows the oracle finding the search item $|001\rangle$. Note that since q_0 is already in the state $|1\rangle$, no additional X gate is applied. However, the other two qubits (q_1 and q_2) are in the state $|0\rangle$. Therefore, they are followed by two X gates. This logic has to be followed for the implementation of other oracles as well.

The matrix representation of the oracle can be expressed as follows.

$$O = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (62)$$

The sample code for constructing oracle circuits for arbitrary search items is given in appendix 8.2.1.

Figure 4-7 2-qubit, 3-qubit, and 4-qubit oracle circuits for selected search items.

4.3.3 Creating the diffusion circuit

The main objective of the diffusor is to amplify the probability of the phase-shifted solution while decreasing the probability of finding the rest of the states, as discussed in the theory section. Starting from the state vector produced by the oracle, the diffusor amplifies the probability amplitude of the correct search item by reflecting the phase-shifted probability amplitude concerning the average over all items. The diffusor circuit follows the same logic for all search items, and therefore it is independent of the search item.

The diffusor circuit for the 2-qubit Grover's algorithm is shown in Figure 4-8.

Figure 4-8 The diffuser circuit for the 2-qubit Grover's algorithm.

The matrix representation of the above diffuser circuit can be introduced as follows, which is in agreement with the theoretical explanation given in the previous section.

$$\text{Diffusor Operator} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (63)$$

Previously, it was proved that the matrix representation of the diffusor operator for an arbitrary number of items N is given as by,

$$\text{Diffusor Operator} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2}{N} - 1 & \frac{2}{N} & \dots & \dots & \frac{2}{N} \\ \frac{2}{N} & \frac{2}{N} - 1 & \frac{2}{N} & \frac{2}{N} & \frac{2}{N} \\ \dots & \frac{2}{N} & \frac{2}{N} - 1 & \frac{2}{N} & \frac{2}{N} \\ \dots & \frac{2}{N} & \frac{2}{N} & \frac{2}{N} - 1 & \frac{2}{N} \\ \frac{2}{N} & \frac{2}{N} & \frac{2}{N} & \frac{2}{N} & \frac{2}{N} - 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (64)$$

The sample code for constructing the general N -qubit diffusor oracle circuit is given in the appendix (section 8.2.2).

Figure 4-9 The diffuser circuits for the 2-qubit Grover's algorithm (top), the 3-qubit Grover's algorithm (middle), and the 4-qubit Grover's algorithm (bottom).

4.3.4 Creating the complete Grover circuit

Initially, all the qubits are put into the superposition state by applying Hadamard gates on each qubit. Then the oracle circuit and the diffusion circuit are applied in order. Finally, the qubits are measured. The complete circuit of the two-qubit Grover's algorithm for the search item $|00\rangle$ is shown in Figure 4-10.

Figure 4-10 The complete circuit for the 2-qubit Grover's algorithm for the search item $|00\rangle$. Note that Hadamard gate initialization is followed by the oracle, and then by the diffuser. Finally, the two qubits are measured.

4.4 Transpiling quantum circuits to utilize different physical qubits on the backend

Once a quantum circuit is designed, it needs to be rescripted to match the topology of a designated quantum device. In general, even though one can introduce any arbitrary quantum gate (which resembles a unitary operator) to the circuit, the circuit has to undergo numerous transformations to make it compatible with the structure of the quantum device. This is mainly due to the fact that a given quantum device has a predefined set of basis gates and a qubit-connectivity graph. These transformations can be achieved using the transpile function available in Qiskit.

Since the error rates of different qubits and basis gates in a device are different, the performance of a circuit depends on the particular choice of physical qubits utilized by the circuit. To investigate this, the same 2-qubit Grover's circuit was constructed using different qubit pairs. Figures 4-11 and 4-12 show two such circuit constructions, along with the respective transpiled circuits.

Figure 4-11 The two-qubit Grover's algorithm designed using qubit 0 and qubit 1 (top). The transpiled circuit shows the final result of the numerous transformations the circuit undergoes in order to match the topology of the selected backend, ibmq_belem (bottom).

Figure 4-12 The two-qubit Grover's algorithm designed using qubit 1 and qubit 3 (top). The transpiled circuit shows the final result of the numerous transformations the circuit undergoes in order to match the topology of the selected backend, `ibmq_belem` (bottom).

4.5 Construction of the quantum random walk search algorithm

The construction of the quantum random walk search algorithm is based on two main operations; the reflection about the state $|B\rangle$, and the reflection about the state $|U\rangle$ as discussed in section 3.6.6.

4.5.1 Reflection about the state $|B\rangle$

In the first step, the uniform superposition state $|U\rangle$ is reflected about $|B\rangle$. This operation can be achieved using a phase oracle which flips the phase of the search item. The phase oracle is implemented by following the same approach used in Grover's algorithm. For example, the 4-qubit phase oracle implemented to find the search item 0110 is shown in Figure 4-13.

Figure 4-13 The 4-qubit phase oracle implemented to find the search item 0110.

4.5.2 Reflection about the state $|U\rangle$

In the second step, previously reflected state $|U'\rangle$ is reflected again about $|U\rangle$. This reflection is achieved using a linear mapping given in equations (49) and (50). This operation requires quantum phase estimation on the operator W , where W is the evolution operator for a single step of the quantum random walk. W consists of two operations, the coin operation C followed by the shift operation S such that $W = S.C$ (see equation (42)). The Grover diffusion operator is used as the coin operator. 4 qubits are needed to represent the node states (the vertices of the hypercube) whereas 2 qubits are required to represent the coin state. The quantum circuit for the composite operator W can be designed as shown in Figure 4-14.

Figure 4-14 The quantum circuit for the composite operator W . It consists of the coin operator followed by the shift operator.

The largest eigenvalue of W is 1, whose corresponding eigenvector is $|U\rangle$, is the uniform superposition of all node and coin basis states. If the phase estimation yields $\theta = 0$ (which means that the eigenvalue is $e^{2\pi \cdot 0} = 1$), then we know that the node state is $|U\rangle$. Any other value of θ implies that the node state is orthogonal to $|U\rangle$, in which case, we need to put a negative sign in front of the state. This operation has the desired effect of reflecting about $|U\rangle$. The circuit shown in Figure 4-15 puts a negative sign in front of the state if $\theta = 0$, and does nothing if $\theta \neq 0$.

Figure 4-15 This circuit puts a negative sign in front of the state if $\theta = 0$, and does nothing if $\theta \neq 0$.

For this particular step, 4 additional qubits are required, which makes the total number of qubits required for the reflection to be 10. As shown in Figure 4-16, initially, the quantum phase estimation operation is performed on W . Then we put a negative sign in front of the state if the phase estimation yields $\theta = 0$ and does nothing for the case of $\theta \neq 0$. Then the phase estimation operation is reversed as the final step.

Figure 4-16 The quantum circuit used for the operation of reflection about the state $|U\rangle$.

The complete circuit for the quantum random walk search algorithm is shown in Figure 4-17. The two consecutive reflections correspond to a rotation towards the superposition state $|G\rangle$, which represents the quantum state of all the marked nodes. This rotation is repeated at most three times which is the optimal number of iterations as explained in the case of Grover's algorithm (see section 3.5.2). It guarantees the maximum probability of finding the vertex. In order to run this quantum algorithm, a quantum processor with at least 10 qubits is required. Since the freely available quantum backends in the IBM quantum computing platform are limited to at most five qubits, we can only simulate it using the Aer simulator.

Figure 4-17 The complete quantum random walk search algorithm can be implemented in QISKIT following the two operations; reflection about the state $|B\rangle$, and reflection about $|U\rangle$.

5 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

5.1 A comparison of Grover's search results: simulator versus IBM quantum processors

We first compare the results for the Grover's algorithm obtained using the Aer simulator with those obtained using the `ibmq_belem` device. We designed the two-qubit Grover's circuit to find the search element 10. Then the circuit was executed for 8192 times on the Aer simulator. For a fair comparison between the results from the simulator and the device, only a single iteration of the Grover's algorithm was executed. Since the simulator mimics the behavior of an ideal quantum computer, the results produced by the simulator can be considered as theoretical results.

After completing all 8192 runs, the simulator returns the number of times each item was found, from which the probability of measuring each item is obtained. After that, the same circuit was executed for the same number of times on `ibmq_belem`, and the probability of measuring each item was obtained. Figure 5-1 compares the results obtained from the simulator with the results obtained from `ibmq_belem`. Figure 5-1 shows that the `ibmq_belem` quantum processor produces results that agree reasonably well with the theoretically-expected results obtained using the simulator.

Figure 5-1 The comparison between the results obtained from the Aer simulator (left) and the `ibmq_belem` device (right) for the 2-qubit Grover's search. It shows that the quantum backend `ibmq_belem` is capable of providing reasonable results for the two-qubit search.

Then the same procedure was repeated for the three-qubit algorithm as shown in Figure 5-2, and for the four-qubit algorithm as shown in Figure 5-3.

Figure 5-2 The comparison between the results obtained from the Aer simulator (left) and the ibmq_belem device (right) results for the 3-qubit Grover's search. The results differ by a considerable amount.

Figure 5-3 The comparison between the results obtained from the Aer simulator (top) and the ibmq_belem device (bottom) for the 4-qubit Grover's search. For the 4-qubit algorithm, ibmq_belem cannot provide reasonable results.

In contrast to the two-qubit search algorithm, figures 5-2 and 5-3 show that there is a substantial difference between the results from the simulator and the device. In particular, Figure 5-3 shows that the ibmq_belem quantum backend does not provide promising results in finding the search element.

5.1.1 Theoretical analysis of the results for the three-qubit algorithm

We observed that the gap between the theoretically expected results and the results obtained from the IBM device was substantial. The main reason behind this deviation was the noise

present in the actual backend. We will now prove that the results obtained from the simulator are indeed correct and that they represent the theoretically expected results. Here, the proof is given for the three-qubit search. The proofs for the two-qubit search and four-qubit search are provided in the appendix.

Assume that the marked search item is $|011\rangle$. As the first step, the qubits are put into superposition by applying Hadamard gates to each of the qubits as shown in Figure 5-4.

Figure 5-4 (Left) The three qubits have been initialized using Hadamard gates. (Right) Bloch sphere representation shows that all three qubits are in $|+\rangle$ state individually.

Figure 5-4 shows the representation of the three qubits (q_0 , q_1 , and q_2) in the complex vector space. After applying Hadamard gates, the three qubits individually occupy the $|+\rangle$ state. The composite state of the three qubits can be expressed as follows.

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|000\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|001\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|010\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|011\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|100\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|101\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|110\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|111\rangle$$

Note that the amplitudes of all items are the same. The basic idea is to amplify the amplitude of the marked item ($|011\rangle$) while reducing the amplitudes of others. Figure 5-5 shows the Q-sphere representation of $|\psi\rangle$. In the Q-sphere representation, the size of each blob is proportional to the probability amplitude of the corresponding basis state.

Figure 5-5 The Q-sphere representation of the initial superposition state. Here, the probability amplitudes of all basis states are equal (12.5%).

Note that all blobs are of the same size which means that they have the same probability amplitude. Also, the blue color conveys that all items are in phase.

The next step is to apply the oracle for the search item $|011\rangle$. As discussed in section 3.4.1, the action of the oracle is to apply a phase shift of -1 to the search item.

The subsequent state ($|\psi_1\rangle$) after the application of the oracle is realized as,

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\psi_1\rangle = O|\psi\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|000\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|001\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|010\rangle - \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|\mathbf{011}\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|100\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|101\rangle \\
 &+ \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|110\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|111\rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 5-6 shows the Q-sphere representation of $|\psi_1\rangle$. The Q-sphere representation shows that the marked search item $|011\rangle$ now has a phase difference of π in contrast to the other items. (Yellow represents an angle of π) However, note that all the items have equal probability amplitudes irrespective of the phase difference.

Figure 5-6 The Q-sphere representation of $|\psi_1\rangle$ shows that the search item $|011\rangle$ now has a phase difference of π , in contrast to the other search items. (Yellow represents an angle of π).

The next step of the Grover's algorithm is to apply the diffusion operator, $U_s = 2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| - I$.

The resultant state $|\psi_2\rangle$ is given by,

$$|\psi_2\rangle = U_s|\psi_1\rangle = (2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| - I)|\psi_1\rangle = 2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|\psi_1\rangle - I|\psi_1\rangle = 2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|\psi_1\rangle - |\psi_1\rangle \quad (65)$$

Note that,

$$\langle\psi|\psi_1\rangle = \frac{1}{8}(1 + 1 + 1 - 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1) = \frac{3}{4}$$

Substituting the result for $\langle\psi|\psi_1\rangle$ in Equation (65).

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi_2\rangle &= 2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|\psi_1\rangle - |\psi_1\rangle = 2\frac{3}{4}|\psi\rangle - |\psi_1\rangle = \frac{3}{2}|\psi\rangle - |\psi_1\rangle \\ &= \frac{3}{2}\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|000\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|001\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|010\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|0\mathbf{11}\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|100\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|101\rangle\right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|110\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|111\rangle\right) \\ &\quad - \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|000\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|001\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|010\rangle - \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|0\mathbf{11}\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|100\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|101\rangle\right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|110\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}}|111\rangle\right) \\ |\psi_2\rangle &= \frac{1}{2\sqrt{8}}|000\rangle + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{8}}|001\rangle + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{8}}|010\rangle + \frac{5}{2\sqrt{8}}|0\mathbf{11}\rangle + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{8}}|100\rangle + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{8}}|101\rangle + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{8}}|110\rangle \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{8}}|111\rangle \end{aligned}$$

The final stage of the Grover's algorithm is to measure the state $|\psi_2\rangle$. This yields the following probabilities.

$$P(x = 011) = \left(\frac{5}{2\sqrt{8}}\right)^2 = \frac{25}{32} = 0.78125$$

$$P(x \neq 011) = \left(\frac{1}{2\sqrt{8}}\right)^2 = \frac{1}{32} = 0.03125$$

These theoretically-expected measurement probabilities agree with the results obtained from the Aer simulator within error bars. The Q-sphere representation of the final state $|\psi_2\rangle$ is shown in Figure 5-7. The size of the blob corresponding to $|011\rangle$ basis state is considerably larger than the others, which indicates that $|011\rangle$ has a much higher probability amplitude.

Figure 5-7 The Q-sphere representation of the final state $|\psi_2\rangle$. The basis state $|011\rangle$ is represented by a blob that is considerably larger than the other basis states. This indicates that $|011\rangle$ basis state has a much higher probability amplitude than the others.

Table 5-1 compares the probabilities of measuring the correct search item obtained using the theoretical analysis with the results obtained through the simulator and the ibmq_belem device, for the 2-qubit, 3-qubit, and 4-qubit search. As expected, the simulation results agree with the theoretical predictions within the error bars.

Table 5-1 Probabilities of measuring the correct search item in the 2-qubit, 3-qubit, and 4-qubit Grover’s search. The table compares the results from the theoretical analysis with the results obtained through the simulator and the ibmq_belem device.

Type of the algorithm	Results from the theoretical analysis (%)	Results from the Aer simulator (%)	Results from the IBM device (%)
2-qubit Grover’s algorithm	100%	(100 ± 0) %	(91.44 ± 0.08) %
3-qubit Grover’s algorithm	78.125%	(78.1 ± 0.2) %	(39 ± 2) %
4-qubit Grover’s algorithm	47.265625%	(47.3 ± 0.3) %	(7.6 ± 0.4) %

The table shows a comparatively small difference between the theoretically predicted results and the results obtained from the IBM device for the two-qubit Grover’s search, and a higher difference for the three-qubit and four-qubit searches. The results obtained using the device in the three-qubit case are about half of the theoretically predicted values. For the four-qubit case, the measurement probability given by the device is unsatisfactorily low. Overall, the results from the IBM device become less promising as the number of qubits increases. Therefore, it is recommended to take other measures to reduce the occurrences of errors in quantum processors when executing quantum algorithms with a higher number of qubits.

5.1.2 Results for finding each search item from different solution spaces

Previously in section 5.1, results obtained for the Grover’s search using the Aer simulator and ibmq_belem device were compared for a particular search item. We now repeat this analysis for all possible 2^n search items in the solution space, where n is the number of qubits.

The results were represented and compared using heat maps. Figures 5-8, 5-9, and 5-10 show results for the 2-qubit, 3-qubit, and 4-qubit search respectively. Note that the search item is denoted as the “marked state” whereas the observed state is denoted as the “measured state”. The color represents the measurement probability. The darker shade represents a higher probability with a maximum value of 1.0, and the lighter shade represents a lower probability with a minimum value of 0.0.

Figure 5-8 Results for the 2-qubit Grover's search obtained using the Aer simulator (left) and ibm_belem device (right). The color represents the measurement probability. The plots indicate only a marginal difference between the results obtained from the simulator and the device.

Figure 5-9 Results for the 3-qubit Grover's search obtained using the Aer simulator (left) and ibm_belem device (right). The color represents the measurement probability. The plots indicate a considerable difference between the results obtained from the simulator and the device.

Figure 5-10 Results for the 4-qubit Grover's search obtained using the Aer simulator (left) and ibm_belem device (right). The color represents the measurement probability. The 4-qubit search on the device does not produce satisfactory results when compared to the simulation results.

Figure 5-8 shows a marginal difference between the results obtained from the simulator and the device for the 2-qubit case, whereas Figure 5-9 shows a considerable gap between the two types of results for the 3-qubit Grover’s algorithm. In contrast to the 2-qubit and 3-qubit search, the 4-qubit search on the device does not produce satisfactory results, as shown in Figure 5-10.

5.2 Comparison of the two-qubit Grover’s search for different connecting qubit pairs

The CNOT gate (also known as the CX gate) is the key gate in the construction of Grover’s algorithm as previously explained. Since different connecting qubit pairs have different error rates, a significant focus should be given to choosing a proper qubit pair when connecting CNOT gates. Table 5-2 shows the gate error percentage for different pairs of connecting qubits in the `ibmq_belem` backend. This is a measure of the readout error of the quantum circuit.

Table 5-2 The connecting qubits in `ibmq_belem` backend and their gate error percentage

Connecting Qubits	Gate error percentage (%)
0-1	1.833
1-0	1.833
1-2	0.988
2-1	0.988
1-3	3.330
3-1	3.330
3-4	3.702
4-3	3.702

The two-qubit Grover’s circuit for the same search item was constructed using different pairs of connecting qubits. Each circuit was then transpiled to match the `ibmq_belem` architecture. Then each circuit was executed on the device, and the probability of measuring the correct search item was recorded. Figure 5-11 shows the measurement probabilities for different qubit pairs.

Figure 5-11 The probability of finding the search element after designing the two-qubit Grover’s algorithm using different two-qubit combinations. 3-4 qubit pair gives the highest probability out of the four combinations considered.

Considering Table 5-1, the qubit pair with qubit 3 and qubit 4 has the highest CX error percentage. But according to Figure 5-11, the same qubit pair gives the highest probability out of all qubit-pair combinations. This suggests that there could be other unknown factors affecting the performance of a given qubit pair, in addition to the gate error percentage.

5.3 Comparison of the results on different backends

Different quantum processors have different error rates and qubit-connectivity graphs, which can positively or negatively impact the results depending on the task. In this study, the effect of the chosen backend on the performance of the Grover’s algorithm was explored. As previously mentioned, the selected backends were chosen to exaggerate the similarities and differences between the freely available quantum backends in IBM Quantum Lab. Figures 5-12, 5-13, and 5-14, respectively, show results for the 2-qubit, 3-qubit, and 4-qubit Grover’s search, obtained using three different 5-qubit devices.

Figure 5-12 A comparison of the results for the 2-qubit Grover's algorithm for the search item 10 on different quantum backends. All three backends were capable of producing reasonable results for the 2-qubit case.

Figure 5-13 A comparison of the results for the 3-qubit Grover's algorithm for the search item 011 on different quantum backends. The backend ibmq_bogota provided a significantly lower probability of finding the correct search item when compared to the other two devices.

Figure 5-14 A comparison of the results for the 4-qubit Grover’s algorithm for the search item 1101 on different quantum backends. All three backends were unable to generate promising results for the 4-qubit search algorithm.

According to Figure 5-12, all three backends showed reasonable results for the 2-qubit Grover’s algorithm. For the 3-qubit case, the quantum backend “ibmq_bogota” provided a much lower probability of finding the search item when compared to the other two devices, as shown in Figure 5-13. The other two backends (“ibmq_belem” and “ibmq_lima”) yield approximately similar probabilities. All three backends were unable to provide satisfactory results for the 4-qubit Grover’s search as shown in Figure 5-14.

5.4 Grover’s search with multiple search items

Although this study has been confined to finding a single search item so far, one can find multiple solutions in the solution space using Grover’s algorithm. When there are multiple search items, a suitable oracle needs to be constructed which applies a phase shift for all search items involved. In this study, we investigated three-qubit Grover’s search with two search items, namely, 100 and 111. The oracle used in this study is shown in the appendix. Figure 5-15 compares the results obtained using the Aer simulator and ibmq_belem device.

Figure 5-15 Results of the three-qubit Grover's search with search items 100 and 111. The graph compares the results obtained through the simulator with the results obtained through the ibmq_belem device.

The simulator yields approximately equal probabilities (close to 50%) for the two search items. The corresponding probabilities yielded by the device are considerably lower than the theoretically expected values, but they are approximately equal.

5.5 The effect of the number of Grover iterations on the performance of the Grover's search

As discussed in Chapter 3, the results of the Grover's algorithm improve when the number of Grover iterations increases. But this behavior was only visible for the three-qubit and four-qubit Grover's searches since the optimal number of iterations for the two-qubit algorithm is one. It was also shown that the results get worse when the optimal number of iterations is exceeded. This specific behavior was further investigated by running the Grover's algorithm for multiple iterations.

5.5.1 2-qubit Grover's algorithm

Figure 5-16 A comparison of the two-qubit Grover's search results obtained using the simulator for a single iteration (left) and two iterations (right). The probability of measuring the search item is substantially decreased when the number of Grover iterations is increased to two. Here, the designated search item is |00).

Figure 5-17 A comparison of the two-qubit Grover's search results obtained using the device for a single iteration (left) and two iterations (right). The probability of measuring the search item is substantially decreased when the number of Grover iterations is increased to two. Here, the designated search item is |00).

Figure 5-16 compares the two-qubit Grover's search results obtained using the simulator for a single iteration and two iterations. Figure 5-17 shows the same comparison for the results obtained using the IBM device. Figures show that for both the simulator and the device, the

probability of measuring the search item declines when running the algorithm for two iterations. Therefore, it is recommended not to repeat the Grover iteration more than once for the two-qubit Grover's search. This observation agreed with the theoretically expected behavior discussed in section 3.5.1.

5.5.2 3-qubit Grover's algorithm

Figure 5-18 A comparison of the three-qubit Grover's search results obtained using the simulator for a single iteration (top left), two iterations (top right), and three iterations (bottom left). The probability of measuring the search item improves up to two iterations, but it declines when running the algorithm beyond two iterations, which is the optimal number of iterations for the three-qubit case. Here, the designated search item is $|010\rangle$.

Figure 5-18 shows a comparison of the three-qubit Grover's search results obtained using the simulator for a single iteration, two iterations, and three iterations. The same comparison for the results obtained using the IBM device is shown in Figure 5-19.

According to Figure 5-18, when running on the simulator, the probability of measuring the search item increases for two Grover iterations. But when the number of iterations exceeds the optimal number of Grover iterations (which is two), the probability declined. In contrast to that, the results obtained using the device continuously get worse as the number of Grover iterations increases.

Figure 5-19 A comparison of the three-qubit Grover's search results obtained using the device for a single iteration (top left), two iterations (top right), and three iterations (bottom left). The probability of measuring the search item gets progressively worse as the number of iterations is increased. Here, the designated search item is $|010\rangle$.

5.5.3 4-qubit Grover's algorithm

Figure 5-20 A comparison of the four-qubit Grover's search results obtained using the simulator for a single iteration (first from top), two iterations (second from top), three iterations (third from top), and four iterations (fourth from top). The probability of measuring the search item improves up to three Grover iterations, but it declines when running the algorithm for three iterations, which is the optimal number of iterations for the four-qubit case. Here, the designated search item is $|0110\rangle$.

Figure 5-21 A comparison of the four-qubit Grover's search results obtained using the device for a single iteration (first from top), two iterations (second from top), three iterations (third from top), and four iterations (fourth from top). In contrast to the results obtained using the simulator, the probability of measuring the search item does not notably change when the number of iterations is increased. Here, the designated search item is $|0110\rangle$.

Figure 5-20 compares the four-qubit Grover’s search results obtained using the simulator for multiple iterations. Figure 5-21 shows the same comparison for the results obtained using the IBM device.

According to Figure 5-20, the results obtained using the simulator improved when the Grover’s operator was repeated up to three iterations. But when the number of iterations exceeds the optimal number (which is three), the results degraded. In contrast to that, there is no notable change in the results obtained using the device when the number of iterations is increased.

It was evident that Grover’s algorithm does not guarantee its best results for a single iteration when the number of qubits in the problem increases. It means that we have to apply multiple Grover iterations, close to its theoretically predicted optimal number. So far, we have considered the probabilities observed for a single marked item. But this procedure can be extended for all possible search elements in the corresponding solution space.

Figure 5-22 A comparison of the four-qubit Grover’s search results obtained using the simulator for a single iteration (top left), two iterations (top right), and three iterations (bottom left). Here, all possible search items in the solution space are considered. The color represents the probability of measuring the correct search item. The results are progressively improved as the number of iterations is increased up to three, which is the optimal number of iterations for the four-qubit case.

Figure 5-22 compares the four-qubit Grover’s search results obtained using the simulator for multiple iterations, for all possible search items in the 4-qubit solution space. This analysis was not repeated for the physical quantum device, since multiple iterations do not improve results in the case of physical devices, as shown earlier.

As shown in Figure 5-22, the results obtained using the simulator are considerably improved for the optimal number of Grover iterations (which is three) compared to a single iteration. The

improvement from two iterations to three iterations was not substantial when compared to that from one iteration to two iterations.

5.6 Mitigating measurement errors using calibration matrices

The occurrence of measurement errors can reduce the accuracy of the results obtained using quantum processors. The inaccurate measurement results can be corrected with the aid of a calibration matrix. The calibration matrix is unique to a given quantum backend. First, a noise model is created specifically for the chosen quantum backend using its existing qubit and gate data. Then all 2^n possible basis states for the n-qubit configuration are prepared and measured promptly.

The probabilities of measuring the prepared state and the other basis states are evaluated and presented in the form of a matrix. The expected results are represented by the diagonal elements, whereas the off-diagonal elements signify the measurement errors (*Measurement Error Mitigation — Qiskit 0.36.0 documentation*; Norlen, 2020). The calibration matrix (see Figure 5-23) is used as input data to correct the erroneous data obtained directly from the quantum backend. The corrected results are anticipated to be better than the results directly obtained using the device.

Figure 5-23 The 2-qubit (top left), 3-qubit (top right), and 4-qubit (bottom left) calibration matrices for the ibmq_belem device. The color shading represents the probability of measuring a particular state given the prepared state.

Here we applied this measurement-error mitigation technique to improve the Grover’s search results obtained using the `ibmq_belem` device. Figure 5-24, 5-25, and 5-26, respectively, show the error-corrected results for the 2-qubit, 3-qubit, and 4-qubit search, along with the results obtained directly from the device and the simulator.

Figure 5-24 Comparison of the results obtained using the simulator, results obtained using the device, and the error-corrected results for the 2-qubit search algorithm.

Figure 5-25 Comparison of the results obtained using the simulator, results obtained using the device, and the error-corrected results for the 3-qubit search algorithm.

The results show that for the 2-qubit and 3-qubit search, the application of the error mitigation technique slightly increases the probability of measuring the correct search item. For the 3-qubit search, the error-corrected probability is still considerably lower than the results obtained from the simulator. For the 4-qubit search, the error mitigation does not provide a noticeable improvement in the results.

We further applied the error-mitigation technique to the 3-qubit Grover’s algorithm with two search items (see Figure 5-27). A slight increase in the probability of measuring both search

items can be observed. Furthermore, the error correction seems to have made the measurement probabilities of the two search items approximately equal.

Figure 5-26 Comparison of the results obtained using the simulator, results obtained using the device, and the error-corrected results for the 4-qubit search algorithm.

Figure 5-27 Comparison of the results obtained using the simulator, results obtained using the device, and the error-corrected results for the 3-qubit search algorithm for two search items (100 and 111).

5.7 The four-qubit quantum random walk search algorithm

Here we present results for the quantum random walk search in 4-qubit solution space. This is analogous to finding a marked vertex of a four-dimensional hypercube. Only the Aer simulator results are available for this analysis since the number of qubits required for the circuit (which is 10) exceeds the total number of qubits in publicly-available IBM backends.

5.7.1 Comparison of the Grover's algorithm and the quantum random walk search algorithm for a single search item

Figure 5-28 compares the results of the Grover's algorithm and the quantum walk search algorithm for a single search item. Both algorithms were run for a single iteration.

Both algorithms provide satisfactory and approximately equal results in determining the marked search item. However, the Grover's algorithm provides a slightly higher probability of measuring the search item when compared to its counterpart.

Figure 5-28 The results obtained using the simulator for the Grover's algorithm (top) and the quantum random walk search algorithm (bottom). The results are approximately close to each other, while Grover's algorithm gives a slightly higher probability of measuring the search item.

5.7.2 The effect of the number of iterations on the performance of the quantum random walk search

Figure 5-29 A comparison of the four-qubit quantum random walk search results obtained using the simulator for a single iteration (first from top), two iterations (second from top), three iterations (third from top), and four iterations (fourth from top). The probability of measuring the search item improves up to three iterations, but it declines when running the algorithm beyond three iterations, which is the optimal number of iterations for the four-qubit quantum random walk search.

Figure 5-29 shows a comparison of the four-qubit quantum random walk search results obtained using the simulator for a single iteration, two iterations, three iterations, and four iterations. According to Figure 5-29, when running on the simulator, the probability of measuring the search item increases for three iterations. But when the number of iterations exceeds the optimal number of Grover iterations (which is three), the probability declined.

The effect of the number of iterations on the performance of Grover’s algorithm can be compared with that of the quantum random walk search as shown in Table 5-3.

Table 5-3 Probabilities of measuring the correct search item in one, two, three, and four Grover iterations. The table compares Grover’s algorithm results and the quantum random walk search results.

Number of iterations	Grover’s search results (%)	Quantum random walk search results (%)
1	(47.3 ± 0.3) %	(46.7 ± 0.2) %
2	(90.82 ± 0.07) %	(88.7 ± 0.1) %
3	(96.06 ± 0.04) %	(93.81 ± 0.05) %
4	(58.4 ± 0.2) %	(61.3 ± 0.1) %

Table 5-3 shows a comparatively small difference in the probability of measuring the search item between the Grover’s search and the quantum random walk search for each number of iterations. The results increase for three Grover iterations for both cases and decline when the number exceeds the optimal number of Grover iterations (which is three).

6 DISCUSSION

When the results obtained using the simulator and the device for Grover's algorithm for all the cases (2-qubit, 3-qubit, and 4-qubit searches) were compared, it was evident that the results provided by the simulator are always the best. The simulator always provides higher probabilities of finding the search item in contrast to the device. The highest probability of finding the search item on a device was achieved for the 2-qubit Grover's algorithm on the backend "ibmq_belem", which was (91.44 ± 0.08) %. For the 3-qubit Grover's search, ibmq_belem provided a lower but reasonable probability of (39 ± 2) %. In contrast to that, the 4-qubit algorithm on ibmq_belem did not provide satisfactory results, since the probability of measuring the correct search item was as low as the probability of measuring an arbitrary item in the search space.

The heat maps presented in section 5.1.2 lead to the same conclusions. These heat maps compare the corresponding measurement probabilities for all possible 2^n search items in the solution space, where n is the number of qubits. Here, the results were presented for a single iteration only. Figure 5-8 showed that the probabilities obtained using the device for measuring the marked state are close to the probabilities obtained using the simulator for the 2-qubit Grover's algorithm. In contrast, the 4-qubit algorithm does not produce reasonable results when compared to the simulation results (see Figure 5-10). However, the 3-qubit Grover's algorithm yielded satisfactory results for a single Grover iteration (see Figure 5-9).

Selecting an appropriate quantum backend was a significant task in this study, due to the differences in the structure, error rates of the gates, processors used, etc. The backend "ibmq_belem" was chosen as the main backend for most of the analysis presented in this thesis since it had a lower relaxation time and a lower dephasing time. Additionally, it was easily accessible most of the time and was less busy throughout the day in contrast to the other devices. The other backends used in the study such as "ibmq_santiago", "ibmq_lima" and "ibmq_bogota" were primarily utilized to emphasize the differences and the similarities among the quantum backends depending on the task.

The CNOT gate is one of the key gates used in Grover's algorithm. Therefore, the error percentages related to the CNOT gate with respect to the connecting qubit pairs were compared. The backend "ibmq_belem" operates on 5 qubits. The gate error percentage for qubit 1 and qubit 2 was the lowest, and it was nearly a quarter of the maximum gate error percentage, which

was observed for qubits 3 and 4. It was suggested that specific attention should be given to the qubit connection of the gates. However, this hypothesis was tested for the 2-qubit case only.

The backends “ibmq_belem”, “ibmq_lima” and “ibmq_bogota” were used to investigate how the Grover search results depend on the choice of the backend. For the 2-qubit and the 3-qubit cases, ibmq_belem and ibmq_lima provided the most accurate results, in contrast to the results yielded by ibmq_bogota. Although there was only a marginal difference between the results obtained from ibmq_bogota and the other two devices for the 2-qubit Grover’s algorithm, the difference was substantial for the 3-qubit case. This suggests that choosing the right backend is certainly important. However, none of the three backends used in this study was able to provide reasonably accurate results for the 4-qubit Grover’s algorithm.

Grover’s algorithm can also be used to find multiple search items in a given search space. For a three-qubit search space with two marked search items, Grover’s algorithm is expected to measure the search items with equal probabilities of 50%. The results obtained using the device yielded approximately equal but lower probabilities for the two search items, which were 36.4% and 32.5%, respectively.

According to the theoretical derivation given in section 3.5.2, there exists an upper bound to the number of Grover iterations that gives the highest possible probability for measuring the search item. It was further proved that the performance declined after surpassing this limit. Therefore, from a theoretical perspective, it is always recommended to use the optimal number of Grover iterations.

In this study, it was observed that the simulator provides the best results for the optimal number of Grover iterations. But in contrast to that, the results obtained using the device progressively get worse as the number of iterations is increased. Therefore, the best results on the device are obtained for a single iteration. The possible reason for this behavior could be the accumulation of errors with the increasing number of iterations, as each additional layer of quantum gates introduces more errors to the circuit. Therefore, we have to be attentive to developing quantum algorithms with a lower number of quantum gates when running on actual quantum processors. In addition, the results obtained using the device can significantly deviate from the results obtained using the simulator as the number of qubits in the algorithm increases.

Measurement errors can reduce the accuracy of the results produced by a quantum processor. The calibration matrix technique was employed to mitigate the impact of measurement errors on the accuracy of the Grover’s search results. Figure 5-23 shows the 2-qubit, 3-qubit, and 4-

qubit calibration matrices for the `ibmq_belem` device. These matrices were utilized as inputs to the backend, and the error-corrected results were observed for each situation separately.

We observed that even though, the error-corrected probabilities were slightly higher than the results obtained from the device, for 2-qubit and 3-qubit Grover's algorithms (see figures 5-24 and 5-25), there was a considerable gap between the error-corrected results and the results provided by the simulator. In addition, there was no improvement in the results for the 4-qubit case after applying this technique (see Figure 5-26). Therefore, the error calibration matrix technique becomes less effective when the number of qubits increases.

The quantum random walk search algorithm seeks to find a marked vertex of a four-dimensional hypercube. As previously mentioned, the total number of qubits in the freely available IBM backends is limited to five. But in order to run the quantum random walk search algorithm, 10 qubits were needed. Therefore, only the results obtained using the Aer simulator were presented in this study.

For the optimal number of iterations, the probability of detecting the correct search item in the 4-qubit Grover's algorithm was $(96.06 \pm 0.04) \%$, while the probability of finding the search item using the quantum random walk search was $(93.81 \pm 0.05) \%$. Therefore, it is evident that the results obtained using the simulator are approximately the same for both algorithms. However, if given the opportunity to access a quantum backend with at least 10 qubits, the results for an actual quantum processor can be obtained. This would be an interesting direction for the continuation of this project.

7 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we implemented the quantum search algorithm (known as the Grover's algorithm) for two, three, and four-qubit search spaces. The algorithm was executed on quantum simulators, as well as on actual quantum processors available via the cloud by IBM Quantum Lab. It was observed that the results from the IBM devices become less promising as the number of qubits increases. In particular, the 4-qubit search on the device did not produce satisfactory results.

The impact of the error rates of quantum gates on the performance of the Grover's search was also investigated. Here, the emphasis was given to CNOT gates. The best and worst-performing qubit pairs were identified by taking the error rate of the CNOT gate into account. However, later it was observed that the error rate of the CNOT gate does not influence the results drastically. In other words, there could be unknown factors related to the internal quantum hardware affecting the performance of a given qubit pair, which would be an interesting topic for further investigation.

The effect of the number of iterations on the performance of the Grover's search was also investigated in this study. It was identified that the results obtained using the simulator are continuously improved until a certain upper limit on the number of iterations is reached. After surpassing this optimal number of iterations, the results start to degrade. Therefore, when using simulators, it is always recommended to run the Grover's search for the optimal number of Grover iterations.

However, unlike the simulator, the results obtained using the device tend to degrade with the application of multiple Grover iterations. It was hypothesized that the errors present in quantum gates accumulate with the repeated application of the Grover operator, resulting in the observed behavior. Therefore, it is recommended to be highly attentive to the errors present in the actual quantum processors, when quantum algorithms are executed on actual quantum backends, particularly for a higher number of qubits.

Measurement error mitigation techniques are capable of reducing the impact of measurement errors in real quantum processors by defining noise models for backends. The error-corrected results obtained using the calibration matrix technique were only reasonable for the two-qubit case and three-qubit case, and also for the three-qubit search with two solutions. Error-corrected results were not promising for the four-qubit Grover's search.

Furthermore, we investigated the quantum random walk search algorithm, which is the quantum equivalent of the classical random walk. Only the results from the simulator could be obtained due to the limited number of qubits in freely available quantum backends. For the 4-qubit search space, the probability of finding the search item using quantum random walk was approximately equal to that of the 4-qubit Grover's algorithm. If access to a quantum processor with at least ten qubits is granted, results for an actual quantum computer can be obtained. This would be an interesting topic to look into in future studies.

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8 APPENDIX

8.1 Oracle circuits for 2-qubit, 3-qubit, and 4-qubit Grover's algorithm implementations

8.1.1 2-qubit Grover's search

Figure 8-1 The complete set of oracles for the 2-qubit Grover's search

8.1.2 3-qubit Grover's search

Figure 8-2 The complete set of oracles for the 3-qubit Grover's search

8.1.3 4-qubit Grover's search

Figure 8-3 The complete set of oracles for the 3-qubit Grover's search

The oracle circuit used for the Grover's search with multiple search items (100 and 111) is shown in Figure 8-4.

Figure 8-4 Oracle used for Grover's search with multiple search items (100 and 111)

8.2 Basic codes used in the study

8.2.1 The sample code for creating a general oracle

```
# General n-qubit phase Oracle for a single search string
def grover_oracle1(search_string):
    n = len(search_string)
    oracle = QuantumCircuit(n)
    oracle.barrier(range(n)) # adding a barrier
    # Indices in 'search_string' where the value is '0'
    nonzero_indices = [i for i, val in enumerate(search_string[::-1])
if val=='0']
    #print(nonzero_indices)
    a = len(nonzero_indices)

    if a == 0:
        oracle.h(n-1)
        oracle.mct(list(range(n-1)), n-1)
        oracle.h(n-1)

    else:
        oracle.x(nonzero_indices)
        oracle.h(n-1)
        oracle.mct(list(range(n-1)), n-1)
        oracle.h(n-1)
        oracle.x(nonzero_indices)

    return oracle
```

The main steps in the sample code can be realized as follows.

1. The `grover_oracle1` function takes a search string as the input. In this case, this is the search element that we intend to find. For example, say $|00\rangle$ in a two-qubit case.
2. Then, the search string is checked in the reverse order to determine the qubits which are in the state $|0\rangle$, since we apply the X gates to them only.
3. The application of the X gates is done, under two situations. If there are no qubits in the state $|0\rangle$, which means all the qubits are in the state $|1\rangle$, all we have to do is, apply the CZ gate. This is performed in the first part of the conditional statement.
4. Under the second condition, after knowing what qubits are in the state $|0\rangle$, the X gates are applied to them only, followed by a CZ gate, which is represented in the second part of the conditional statement.
5. In both cases, the gates are again applied in the reverse order to balance out the circuit.

8.2.2 The sample code for creating a general diffusor

```
# Diffusion operator for the general n-qubit Grover's search
def diffusion_operator(n):
    diffusion = QuantumCircuit(n)

    diffusion.barrier(range(n)) # adding a barrier

    diffusion.h(range(n))

    diffusion.x(range(n))
    diffusion.h(n-1)
    diffusion.mct(list(range(n-1)), n-1)
    diffusion.h(n-1)

    diffusion.x(range(n))

    diffusion.h(range(n))

    return diffusion
```

The main steps in the sample code can be realized as follows.

1. The function “diffusion_operator” takes the number of qubits as the input. In the case of the 2-qubit circuit, the input should be 2.
2. Then, it puts all the qubits into superposition by applying Hadamard gates to all of them, followed by X gates to each of the qubits.
3. Secondly, to get the phase kickback effect in the middle, the multi-controlled Z gate is created as discussed under the Oracle operation.
4. Finally, the gates are again applied in the reverse order to balance out the circuit.

8.2.3 The sample code for creating a general full Grover circuit

```
def create_grover(oracle,diffusion):
    groverCircuit = QuantumCircuit(n)

    groverCircuit.h(range(n))
    groverCircuit.barrier((range(n)))

    # to find the number of iterations
    from math import sqrt, pow, pi
    m = int(pi/4*(sqrt(pow(2,n))))

    for k in range(m):
        groverCircuit+=oracle
        groverCircuit+=diffusion

    groverCircuit.measure_all()
    return(groverCircuit)
```

The main steps in the sample code can be realized as follows.

1. The function “create_grover” takes the oracle circuit and the diffusion circuit as the inputs.
2. Initially, as mentioned above, Hadamard gates are applied to all the qubits which are followed by a barrier. The barrier is supportive in holding the circuit while transpiling since there are a lot of gates followed by the initialization step.
3. After that, the oracle circuit and the diffusor circuit are added in order. To have a better result in Grover’s algorithm, the same couple of circuits (the oracle and the diffusor) should be repeated a few times as shown in the theory section. The calculation is performed within the algorithm to find the optimal number of repetitions.
4. Then, the oracle circuit and the diffusor circuit are added in an orderly, and the number of iterations is equal to the optimal number of repetitions.
5. Eventually, the qubits are measured.

8.3 Theoretical analysis of the results for the two-qubit algorithm

Assume that the marked search item is $|10\rangle$. As the first step, the qubits are put into superposition by applying Hadamard gates to each of the qubits as shown in Figure 8-5.

Figure 8-5 (Left) The two qubits have been initialized using Hadamard gates. (Right) Bloch sphere representation shows that both qubits are in the $|+\rangle$ state individually.

Figure 8-5 shows the representation of the two qubits (q_0 and q_1) in the complex vector space. After applying Hadamard gates, the two qubits individually occupy the $|+\rangle$ state. The composite state of the two qubits can be expressed as follows.

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{2}|00\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|01\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|10\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|11\rangle$$

Note that the amplitudes of all items are the same. The basic idea is to amplify the amplitude of the marked item ($|10\rangle$) while reducing the amplitudes of others. Figure 8-6 shows the Q-sphere representation of $|\psi\rangle$. In the Q-sphere representation, the size of each blob is proportional to the probability amplitude of the corresponding basis state.

Figure 8-6 The Q-sphere representation of the initial superposition state. Here, the probability amplitudes of all basis states are equal (25%).

Note that all blobs are of the same size which means that they have the same probability amplitude. Also, the blue color conveys that all items are in phase.

The next step is to apply the oracle for the search item $|10\rangle$. As discussed in section 3.4.1, the action of the oracle is to apply a phase shift of -1 to the search item.

The subsequent state ($|\psi_1\rangle$) after the application of the oracle is realized as,

$$|\psi_1\rangle = O|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{2}|00\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|01\rangle - \frac{1}{2}|10\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|11\rangle$$

Figure 8-7 shows the Q-sphere representation of $|\psi_1\rangle$. The Q-sphere representation shows that the marked search item $|10\rangle$ now has a phase difference of π in contrast to the other items. (Yellow represents an angle of π) However, note that all the items have equal probability amplitudes irrespective of the phase difference.

Figure 8-7 The Q-sphere representation of $|\psi_1\rangle$ shows that the search item $|10\rangle$ now has a phase difference of π , in contrast to the other search items. (Yellow represents an angle of π).

The next step of the Grover's algorithm is to apply the diffusion operator, $U_s = 2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| - I$.

The resultant state $|\psi_2\rangle$ is given by,

$$|\psi_2\rangle = U_s|\psi_1\rangle = (2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| - I)|\psi_1\rangle = 2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|\psi_1\rangle - I|\psi_1\rangle = 2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|\psi_1\rangle - |\psi_1\rangle \quad (66)$$

Note that,

$$\langle\psi|\psi_1\rangle = \frac{1}{4}(1 + 1 - 1 + 1) = \frac{1}{2}$$

Substituting the result for $\langle\psi|\psi_1\rangle$ in Equation (66).

$$\begin{aligned}
|\psi_2\rangle &= 2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|\psi_1\rangle - |\psi_1\rangle = 2\frac{1}{2}|\psi\rangle - |\psi_1\rangle \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{2}|00\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|01\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|10\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|11\rangle\right) - \left(\frac{1}{2}|00\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|01\rangle - \frac{1}{2}|10\rangle + \frac{1}{2}|11\rangle\right) \\
&= |10\rangle
\end{aligned}$$

The final stage of the Grover's algorithm is to measure the state $|\psi_2\rangle$. This yields the following probabilities.

$$P(x = 10) = (1)^2 = 1$$

$$P(x \neq 10) = (0)^2 = 0$$

These theoretically-expected measurement probabilities agree with the results obtained from the Aer simulator within error bars. The Q-sphere representation of the final state $|\psi_2\rangle$ is shown in Figure 8-8. Note that $|10\rangle$ basis state is the only one existing in the complex vector space.

Figure 8-8 The Q-sphere representation of the final state $|\psi_2\rangle$. Only $|10\rangle$ state remains in the complex vector space.

8.4 Theoretical analysis of the results for the four-qubit algorithm

Assume that the marked search item is $|011\rangle$. As the first step, the qubits are put into superposition by applying Hadamard gates to each of the qubits as shown in Figure 8-9.

Figure 8-9 (Left) The four qubits have been initialized using Hadamard gates. (Right) Bloch sphere representation shows that both qubits are in the $|+\rangle$ state individually.

Figure 8-9 shows the representation of the three qubits (q_0 , q_1 , q_2 , and q_3) in the complex vector space. After applying Hadamard gates, the three qubits individually occupy the $|+\rangle$ state. The composite state of the three qubits can be expressed as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\psi\rangle = & \frac{1}{4} |0000\rangle + \frac{1}{4} |0001\rangle + \frac{1}{4} |0010\rangle + \frac{1}{4} |0011\rangle + \frac{1}{4} |0100\rangle + \frac{1}{4} |0101\rangle + \frac{1}{4} |0110\rangle \\
 & + \frac{1}{4} |0111\rangle + \frac{1}{4} |1000\rangle + \frac{1}{4} |1001\rangle + \frac{1}{4} |1010\rangle + \frac{1}{4} |1011\rangle + \frac{1}{4} |1100\rangle \\
 & + \frac{1}{4} |1101\rangle + \frac{1}{4} |1110\rangle + \frac{1}{4} |1111\rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 8-10 The Q-sphere representation of the initial superposition state. Here, the probability amplitudes of all basis states are equal (6.25%).

Note that the amplitudes of all items are the same. The basic idea is to amplify the amplitude of the marked item ($|1101\rangle$) while reducing the amplitudes of others. Figure 8-10 shows the Q-sphere representation of $|\psi\rangle$. In the Q-sphere representation, the size of each blob is proportional to the probability amplitude of the corresponding basis state.

Note that all blobs are of the same size which means that they have the same probability amplitude. Also, the blue color conveys that all items are in phase.

The next step is to apply the oracle for the search item $|1101\rangle$. As discussed in section 3.4.1, the action of the oracle is to apply a phase shift of -1 to the search item.

The subsequent state ($|\psi_1\rangle$) after the application of the oracle is realized as,

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\psi_1\rangle = O|\psi\rangle &= \frac{1}{4}|0000\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|0001\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|0010\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|0011\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|0100\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|0101\rangle \\
 &+ \frac{1}{4}|0110\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|0111\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|1000\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|1001\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|1010\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|1011\rangle \\
 &+ \frac{1}{4}|1100\rangle - \frac{1}{4}|1101\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|1110\rangle + \frac{1}{4}|1111\rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 8-11 shows the Q-sphere representation of $|\psi_1\rangle$. The Q-sphere representation shows that the marked search item $|011\rangle$ now has a phase difference of π in contrast to the other items. (Yellow represents an angle of π) However, note that all the items have equal probability amplitudes irrespective of the phase difference.

Figure 8-11 The Q-sphere representation of $|\psi_1\rangle$ shows that the search item $|1101\rangle$ now has a phase difference of π , in contrast to the other search items. (Yellow represents an angle of π).

The next step of the Grover's algorithm is to apply the diffusion operator, $U_s = 2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi| - I$.

The resultant state $|\psi_2\rangle$ is given by,

$$|\psi_2\rangle = U_s|\psi_1\rangle = (2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|-I)|\psi_1\rangle = 2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|\psi_1\rangle - I|\psi_1\rangle = 2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|\psi_1\rangle - |\psi_1\rangle \quad (67)$$

Note that,

$$\langle\psi|\psi_1\rangle = \frac{1}{16}(1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 - 1 + 1 + 1) = \frac{12}{16} = \frac{3}{4}$$

Substituting the result for $\langle\psi|\psi_1\rangle$ in Equation (67).

$$|\psi_2\rangle = 2|\psi\rangle\langle\psi|\psi_1\rangle - |\psi_1\rangle = 2\frac{3}{4}|\psi\rangle - |\psi_1\rangle = \frac{3}{2}|\psi\rangle - |\psi_1\rangle$$

After substituting for $|\psi\rangle$ and $|\psi_1\rangle$, the final stage of the Grover's algorithm is to measure the state $|\psi_2\rangle$. This yields the following probabilities.

$$P(x = 1101) = \left(\frac{11}{16}\right)^2 = \frac{121}{256} = 0.47265625$$

$$P(x \neq 1101) = \left(\frac{3}{16}\right)^2 = \frac{9}{256} = 0.03515625$$

These theoretically-expected measurement probabilities agree with the results obtained from the Aer simulator within error bars. The Q-sphere representation of the final state $|\psi_2\rangle$ is shown in Figure 8-12. The size of the blob corresponding to $|1101\rangle$ basis state is considerably larger than the others, which indicates that $|1101\rangle$ has a much higher probability amplitude.

Figure 8-12 The Q-sphere representation of the final state $|\psi_2\rangle$. The basis state $|1101\rangle$ is represented by a blob that is considerably larger than the other basis states. This indicates that $|1101\rangle$ basis state has a much higher probability amplitude than the others.